

EXPLORING SPINNAKER

Supervisor: Dr André Grüning

Justin Man
6263667

I. Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Dr André Grüning and Dr Brian Gardner for their support in helping me understand the complexities of computational neuroscience and investigate the intricacies of the SpiNNaker neuromorphic hardware.

Special thanks to my family and friends who were unrelenting in their support.

II. Declaration of Originality

I confirm that the submitted work is my own work and that I have clearly identified and fully acknowledged all material that is entitled to be attributed to others (whether published or unpublished) using the referencing system set out in the programme handbook. I agree that the University may submit my work to means of checking this, such as the plagiarism detection service Turnitin® UK. I confirm that I understand that assessed work that has been shown to have been plagiarised will be penalised.

III. Abstract

This report explores the capabilities and limitations of the SpiNNaker neuromorphic computing platform by extending the current sPyNNaker API to implement a compartmental neuron model capable of distinguishing between multiple excitatory inputs. The implemented model successfully achieves this and a novel approach to implement more complex learning rule is proposed that utilises a modulating signal to initiate learning. These novel contributions take initial exploratory steps to inform the development of next generation neuromorphic hardware and software.

IV. Statement of Ethics

The project is concerned with investigating and extending the capabilities of the SpiNNaker neuromorphic platform in neural modelling. While all ethical consequences cannot be totally anticipated, the importance of addressing legal, societal, ethical and professional (LSEP) concerns and acting legally and ethically is still important. The following is a discussion of how the project has taken into account LSEP issues.

Legal considerations

This refers to the obligations imposed on persons by the UK legal framework with regard to the use of computing systems. The following are legal implications deemed relevant to the work conducted on this project:

- Computer Misuse Act (Legislation.gov.uk, n.d.)
- Data protection Act (Gov.uk, n.d.)

Computer misuse Act

Introduced in 1990, this law addressed offences related to computer hacking and gaining unauthorised access to computing material.

In the project, precautions were taken to protect against unauthorised access to computer material. The project involved running neural simulations to gather results, stored on a PC. Suitable measures

such as protecting the machine with a password and biometric scanner were taken to prevent unauthorised access to data related to neural simulations. Additionally, antivirus software was used to ensure that no malicious software was on the PC that could lead to unauthorised access to experimental data. Other suitable measures were taken to avoid leaving the PC unattended in public spaces by keeping possession of the machine at all times and to not leave it out in open spaces for extended periods of time.

In the event that the same PC will be used to continue the research using data from real human participants, these actions taken align with the “Public Interest” set of standards in the BCS Code of Conduct (Bcs.org, n.d.) by regarding the protection of personal identifiable data to prevent unlawful disclosure.

Data protection Act

The project did not utilise data from human subjects because the emphasis of the project outcome was focused with the biological accuracy of the software in handling neuron inputs. This has meant fake data in the form of arbitrarily defined spike trains were sufficient to test dynamics of the neuron to which informed consent does not apply, as well as keeping the data confidential.

However, the software created could be integrated into the production versions of the sPyNNaker API for use in neural simulations in a variety of domains as part of the wider EU Human Brain Project. The medical domain is one such example that the SpiNNaker platform is targeted towards which the developed software may be applied to. In this case brain activity data linked to human participants will need to be collected which may involve spike train data to reproduce neuronal activity. In addition, personal identifiable data such as age, gender and marital status may need to be collected to inform the demographic of medical research.

This will have legal implications on informed consent and the protection of data privacy, covered by the Data Protection Act (DPA). Human Brain Project researchers will need to take measures to suitably inform participants of the data being collected and to what extent the data will be used for. This will comply with the DPA in using the data for limited and stated purposes (Gov.uk, n.d.). Other suitable measures in compliance with the DPA include processing the data securely which can be achieved by adopting the same measures as this project regarding the use of secure passwords and biometric authentication mechanisms.

Societal considerations

It is vital to take into account the impact of the project outputs in benefiting society and human wellbeing. It could be argued that the aim of computing professionals should be to maximise human flourishing through computing systems for the public good and to do no harm.

The project aims have been aligned to encourage the following contributions to society and human wellbeing:

Understanding the human brain

The project is afflicted with the wider EU Human Brain Project, a collaboration of a number of research institutions to build ICT system to emulate with accuracy the computational capabilities of the human brain. It is hoped that this will enable researchers to advance knowledge computing, computational neuroscience and brain related medicine. The research that has been conducted illuminates the relatively novel concept of neuromorphic computing platforms to the wider

community by reporting on the hardware and software architecture of the SpiNNaker system, along with an extensive overview of the host-based application programming interface sPyNNaker.

This research contributes to the Human Brain Project by acting as a more comprehensive informational source to adequately inform researchers that are unfamiliar with the technology. Researchers can apply the knowledge provided by this report to develop new methods of neural modelling. An effect of this is the advancement of techniques to treat brain related diseases. These techniques can be applied to debilitating conditions such a dementia to find new ways of preventing, treating and predicting the onset of the disease. In this way, the project outcomes contribute to the overall mission of the Human Brain Project.

Developing next generation neuromorphic hardware

The project aims to extend the current capabilities of the SpiNNaker platform by introducing novel neuron modelling techniques. This increases the capacity of SpiNNaker to support more complex neural simulations informing next generation neuromorphic hardware. This can facilitate the advancement of new discoveries in areas that the Human Brain Project is concerned with involving

- Making available neuromorphic computing architectures to more mainstream use
- Understanding brain cognition
- More complex neural simulations leading to greater understanding of areas in brain related medicine

These implications maintain consistency in accordance with the public interest sections of the BCS code of conduct to have due regard for the public health and wellbeing of others.

Ethical considerations

While the legal system accounts for a set of obligations reflecting moral extremes, there are instances where an action can be legal but not ethical. This is due to ethics being based on an underlying moral code that consists of no single definition. Cultural issues and societal attitudes have an effect on the interpretation of a moral code and this can differ from individuals to countries. Therefore, what is considered ethical from one point of view could also be considered unethical from another.

It could be argued that the project is indeed ethical due to the simple reason that the research conducted was done with a genuine ethical aim of advancing the field of neuromorphic computing, computational neuroscience and promoting human wellbeing for reasons outlined in Societal Considerations. Practically, this ethical perspective has been evidenced by reporting on the benefits and deficiencies of aspects the SpiNNaker technology in an objective, impartial manner. There are no further comments on how deficiencies can be taken advantage of for malicious purposes or false claims about the SpiNNaker system. Within the analysis of designs for neuron model and learning rule along with evaluations of outputs, the positive implications of results are emphasised.

This ethical motivation is further supported with the ACM Code of Ethics (Acm.org, n.d.) where it aligns most clearly with 1.3 of general moral imperatives. Care has been taken to provide full disclosure of system limitations and problems to the best of the researcher's acquired knowledge.

However, it could be argued that the project outcomes can be used for harm to society. The developed system could be used by some to add advanced functionality to the SpiNNaker system to achieve malicious purposes. For instance, a design for a learning algorithm implementation compatible with SpiNNaker is introduced. This could be used to facilitate the creation of malicious

software to run on SpiNNaker or contribute to the development of an advanced machine intelligence utilising human based cognitive capabilities for destructive purposes. This can be considered unethical since it goes directly against public interest outlined in the BCS code of conduct and section 1.2 of the ACM code of ethics by encouraging harm towards others.

In conclusion, the project is deemed ethical because it has been completed with the perspective of how it can benefit society. By virtue of this motivation the project can be considered ethical.

Professional Considerations

Professional competency and integrity refers to actions taken to remain credible in the context of the professional environment. According to the BCS code this includes actions contributing to professional development, seeking out and adopting appropriate standards and being truthful when claiming expertise in an IT area.

The following is an elaboration of the steps that have been taken to maintain professional competency and integrity in the professional project.

Throughout the stages of the project, communication with research partners was vital for gathering information about the design of the SpiNNaker system and implementation approaches. To achieve this the “SpiNNaker Users Group” online forum along with emailing were used. Professional integrity was maintained through the use of appropriate language to convey questions and clarify understanding with research partners who were SMEs in the SpiNNaker technology. This ensured a constructive professional relationship was developed through email that respected the recipients. Section 4d of the BCS code of conduct was followed by acting with integrity and respect towards members from other professions when collaborating in a professional capacity.

Another action employed to maintain professional competency and comply with regulations was to avoid claiming competency that was not possessed and be proactive in developing competency for the project demands. Key challenges of the project were discussed in the introduction to provide clarity on the level of competency possessed at the start of the project. Section 2b of the BCS code of conduct was followed in this instance. Following regulations set in the BCS code of conduct and ACM professional responsibilities referring to professional behaviour extensive background research into SpiNNaker was conducted. This included independent research into the underlying technology and reading relevant documentation to acquire knowledge of the sPyNNaker and PyNN APIs. From these activities point 2a of the BCS code of conduct was followed to undertake work within the author’s competency. In addition, section 2.2 of the ACM code of ethics was met in continually developing knowledge of the capabilities of the SpiNNaker hardware when using and extending the sPyNNaker API.

To remain professional, due regard was given to the confidentiality of persons involved. Persons that were involved in the project apart from the author and supervisor such as those the author collaborated with are only referred to as research partners or SME’s. This action was taken to respect the privacy of individuals who may not wish to be named.

Section 1.6 of the ACM code of ethics expands on giving proper credit for intellectual property. This regulation was closely followed when using the appropriate sources to support ideas and claims throughout the project. Inline referencing was used to credit work done by other’s along with a bibliography and established academic referencing conventions were strictly followed to comply with University regulations as well as industry regulations for BCS and ACM.

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1.0 Introduction

The brain is an extraordinary mechanism, capable of achieving unique human feats and contains on average 86.1 +/- 8.1 billion neurons (Azevedo et al., 2009). This makes modelling the human brain as one system a difficult problem due to its complexities. Traditional computers are capable to modelling aspects of brain function but fall short due to their deterministic von-Neumann architecture. A new type of computer architecture has recently been developed that is inspired by the human brain known as neuromorphic platforms. It is envisioned that this approach could facilitate greater accuracy in brain modelling as the underlying hardware more resembles the neuro-biological architectures present in the brain. The SpiNNaker system is one example at the cutting-edge of scientific research. It offers a hybrid approach, combining digital timing approaches with the asynchronous nature of the human brain. The purpose of this project is to perform novel research to showcase the capabilities of SpiNNaker and its potential in modelling more complex neurons and learning paradigms.

1.1 Motivation

The University of Surrey and other research institutions are working in conjunction with the EU Human Brain Project (HBP) whose ambition is to build a full scale model of the human brain to accelerate advancements in the areas of neuroscience, computing and brain related medicine (Humanbrainproject.eu, 2017). The implications of this the HBP are far ranging and could lead to a greater understanding of the human brain to improve treatments for debilitating brain diseases as well as informing the development of next generation computer hardware. This project is a dynamic area of research and is at the forefront of scientific enquiry into one of the most complex biological systems in nature: the human brain. The HBP is split into many sub-projects (European Commission, 2016) and the particular Sub-Projects this project is afflicted with are Sub-Project 4 (SP4: Mathematical and Theoretical Foundations of Brain Research) and Sub-Project 9 (SP9: Neuromorphic Computing Platform) as advised by the Final Year Project supervisor.

1.1.2 Problem areas

Neuromorphic computing platforms are very much in its infancy and only small subset of functions have been made available. This represents a challenge for this project as little is known about the capabilities of these systems and this represents great potential but also greater risk as the limitations of these systems have not been fully explored.

1.2 Aims

Given the novelty of the technology, the aim of this project is to understand and report on capabilities and limitations of SpiNNaker and to extend the neuromorphic platform to facilitate more complex neural simulations.

1.3 Objectives

To achieve this aim the following project objectives are proposed:

- Research the hardware architecture of the SpiNNaker platform
- Research the design architecture of the sPyNNaker API to gain a thorough understanding of important functions for neural modelling.
- Extend the sPyNNaker architecture by implementing a compartmental neuron model based on a biological pyramidal neuron
- Identify an algorithmic implementation approach of the Urbanczik-Senn (Urbanczik and Senn, 2014) plasticity rule suitable for SpiNNaker that utilises the implemented neuron model
- Bring the implementation approach of the plasticity rule to a suitable stage to take forward into future work and document it

1.4 Success Criteria

The criteria to judge the success of the project: The neuron model can successfully distinguish between two excitatory inputs and an algorithm for the Urbanczik-Senn learning rule is proposed that complies with the restraints imposed by the sPyNNaker API.

1.5 Personal Objectives

The following are personal objectives of the author:

1. Develop research experience
2. Gain knowledge of biological principles relating to the human brain
3. Gaining knowledge of computational neuroscience
4. Develop knowledge of C and Python programming languages

1.6 Report structure

Biological background – a basic introduction of the field of neuroscience and computational neuroscience related to the areas of neuron modelling and learning in the brain.

Technology review – an overview of the state of the art of neuromorphic computing is given along with a more detailed examination of the SpiNNaker hardware architecture, programming model and sPyNNaker API.

Problem analysis - The problem areas which this project intends to address is outlined in more detail.

Design choices –Technology choices and design methodology is documented.

Implementation – the implementation of the neuron and learning rule is detailed in this section along with the problems encountered.

Results and Evaluation of outputs – a discussion of the experiments that are to be conducted are detailed. These experiments are run to test the neuron and the results are analysed and evaluated.

Conclusion – this involves a critical review of project objectives, elaborating upon future work and final reflections of the project.

2.0 Biological Background

The biological background review will focus on the theory of neural modelling relevant to this project.

2.1 Neuron anatomy

Multipolar neurons comprise the majority of neurons found in the human body. Their main operation is to respond to stimuli and transmit electrical signals named action potentials to convey information to other neurons.

2.1.1 Membrane potential

To undergird the concept of membrane potential, positive and negative charge in electricity would be helpful to consider.

In electricity, certain regions of the human body are more positively charged than other regions. This requires a membrane to separate and maintain the charge in these regions. Another function of the membrane is to build potential. The opposite charges are attracted to each other to convert electricity into another form of energy. In this context, voltage measures potential energy generated by separated charges. Current is the ordered directional flow of electricity between two points. Resistance is the insulator to current and blocks or reduces the flow of current. Thus, current can be seen as:

Current = voltage / resistance

These concepts can also be applied to the context of neurons in the human brain when looking at membrane potential. In the human brain voltage is measured in milli-volts (mV). The resting membrane potential is -70mV.

2.1.2 Action potential

The action potential is the primary way a neuron communicates and is an electrical impulse fired by the soma of a neuron when the charge of its membrane potential rises above the firing threshold.

2.1.3 Threshold potential

This refers to the voltage at which the neuron fires an action potential and is approximately -55mV. The membrane potential has to cross this threshold for the neuron to fire an action potential.

Figure 1: Key parts of a cortical neuron (Readingroom.mindspec.org, n.d.).

2.1.4 The Soma

The soma contains the cell nucleus of the neuron and acts as the cell body, containing other essential components such as mitochondria, ribosomes and cytoplasm to maintain cell function. The soma processes input and determines if a neuron activates by firing an electrical impulse.

2.1.5 Dendrites

Dendrites help to influence if the neuron activates by receiving inputs from the pre-synaptic terminals and passing them to the soma to process.

2.1.6 The Axon

The axon is the neuron's primary channel to transmit electrical impulses away from the soma to other neurons.

2.1.7 Myelin

The Myelin is a sheath is a plasma membrane wrapped around the axon that acts as an insulating layer to separate the charge inside the neuron from the charge outside of it. The reason for this is facilitate neuronal dynamics by regulating the charge inside the neuron through gated ion channels to increase the transmission speed of an action potential.

2.1.8 Synapses

Synapses constitute the meeting point between two neurons and are made up of a presynaptic terminal (the neuron firing) at the end of an axon, a 'gap' known as the synaptic cleft and post-synaptic receptors (neuron receiving the input) usually on the dendrite or cell body itself. Receptors receive the action potential emitted by the soma and translate it to a different type of signal using neurotransmitters contained in vesicles. The neurotransmitters determining the input are released and travel through the synaptic cleft to bind onto to the post synaptic receptors of the neuron connected to it.

Figure 2: A synapse formed by a pre and post synaptic terminal (Reality Bites, 2013).

2.2 Synaptic operation and communication

2.2.1 Neurotransmitters

Typically, action potentials are not transmitted directly between synapses as the electrical signal must be chemically converted to cross the synaptic cleft. The reason for this is that neurons communicate electrically through propagating action potentials along its axon and operate chemically at the synapse. The action potential must be converted so that it can travel through the synaptic cleft. Synaptic vesicles pictured in the above figure hold thousands of what are called neuro-transmitters that shape the input of an action potential.

Neurotransmitters are chemicals in the brain that enable chemical transmission of an action potential through the chemical synapse.

When an action potential travels to the pre-synaptic terminal, it activates voltage gated ion channels that release positively charged calcium ions into the neuron's internal cytoplasm. This causes the membrane of the synaptic vesicles to fuse with the neuron's cell membrane and release the neurotransmitters which either diffuse in the synaptic cleft or bind to receptors on the post-synaptic neuron. This process initiates the conversion of the chemical signal back into an electrical signal. Depending on the type of neurotransmitters that bind to types of receptors, the post-synaptic neuron may receive an inhibitory electrical signal that decreases the charge inside the neuron or an excitatory signal which increases the charge.

Neurotransmitters attaching to a receptor determine if an action potential is triggered by increasing or decreasing the charge inside the neuron, pushing it further away from the threshold or closer to triggering an action potential. The operation of increasing the positive charge in a neuron is known as depolarisation and decreasing the positive charge is called hyperpolarisation.

It is important to note that neurons may have hundreds or thousands of synapses that are receiving an inhibitory or excitatory signal shaped by the neurotransmitters. All of the inhibitory inputs are accumulated and also all the excitatory inputs to determine if the post-synaptic membrane crosses the firing threshold to initiate an action potential.

Figure 3: A visual representation on synaptic transmission between the pre-synaptic neuron (Top) and post synaptic neuron (Bottom) (Moyes and Schulte, n.d.).

2.3 Biological synaptic plasticity

Synaptic plasticity is term given to the ability of synapses to influence the firing of other synapses connected to it. As we learn new things throughout or lives the synapses in our brain form new connections and it is in the strength of the connections that are formed that indicate the short or long term change in synaptic efficacy (Vreeken, 2003).

Ion channels are stimulated by neuro-transmitters and either open or close, altering the flow of ions through it and causing a change in the membrane potential of the post synaptic cell. The changes that are induced can be either inhibitory or excitatory, where the strength of a synapse is determined by the degree of voltage change in the post synaptic neuron.

The key factor that determines LTP or LTD is the timing of pre and post synaptic spikes. There is a critical window for synaptic plasticity being 20ms before or after an action potential.

The strengthening of synapses is known a long term potentiation (LTP) is where the change in membrane potential invoked by the pre-synaptic neuron is greater than the post-synaptic neuron. This is where the pre-synaptic neuron fires **before** the post synaptic neuron within the preceding 20ms. The weakening of synaptic connections is known as long term depression where the change in potential at the pre-synaptic neuron is smaller than the post synaptic neuron. LTD is evoked when the pre-synaptic neuron fires **after** the post synaptic neuron within the following 20ms. This is known as Spike Timing Dependant Plasticity (STDP).

Figure 4: (a) LTP resulting 25 minutes after a 100-Hz stimulation. (b) LTD resulting from a 1-Hz stimulation. Adapted from (Leonard, n.d.).

2.4 Modelling neurons

2.4.1 Spike trains

A spike train is an encoded message of a neuron represented as time series sequence of action potentials. It is believed that the spatial structure of the action potential carries minimal information and can be encoded as a stream of binary event, where 0 represents no spike occurrence and 1 denotes a spike. Spike trains can be plotted to visualise the spike output of a neuron over time in a spike raster plot, showing a collection of simultaneous binary spike trains, where each line represents an action potential embedded in a spike train shown by Figure 5.

Figure 5: An example of a spike raster plot (McTavish, n.d.).

2.4.2 Spike encoding

Neural encoding is concerned with how neurons represent information with action potentials in an individual cell or network of neurons (Nature.com, 2017). It is thought that digital and analog information can be encoded by neurons but it is still unclear whether neurons use rate or temporal coding (En.wikipedia.org, 2017). A brief description of each of the main neural coding schemes are presented.

Rate coding - a traditional coding scheme characterised by the frequency or rate of action potentials. Rate coding assumes that most of the information is contained in the neuron firing rate and calculating this value is important when using this coding scheme (En.wikipedia.org, 2017). Information relating to the timing of a spike train is dismissed as 'noise' making rate coding inefficient but robust. Recent research has suggested that the firing rate concept that rate coding relies on is not complex enough to accurately describe brain activity (Stein, Gossen and Jones, 2005).

Temporal coding – a coding scheme that uses the precise timing between spikes to encode information. In contrast to rate coding, temporal coding factors in 'noise' generated by random fluctuations in firing rate in biological neurons. This coding scheme suggests that it can be used to encode information down to millisecond time level (Eckmiller, 1991). A binary system of 1/0 is used to express this coding scheme– 1 is a spike and 0 is not a spike (Theunissen and Miller, 1995). Based on the observations this coding scheme will be adopted for use in spike trains for neural simulations for this project as the SpiNNaker project also uses this scheme.

Population coding – this coding scheme focuses on patterns of spike trains in a set of neurons to determine some value about the inputs (En.wikipedia.org, 2017). Benefits of using this coding scheme include less uncertainty due to neuron variability in statistical analysis, a greater number of different stimulus attributes can be represented and faster turnaround in results compared to rate coding (Hubel and Wiesel, 1959). This coding scheme has been deemed unsuitable for use in this project as it is mainly used for sensor and motor areas of the brain. This contrasts with the focus of this project which is concerned with cortex neurons found in the pre-frontal cortex responsible for learning.

2.4.3 Neuron models

The following models aim to describe how the membrane voltage changes in response to action potentials.

The Hodgkin–Huxley model

Alan Lloyd Hodgkin and Andrew Huxley are best known for their work on the Hodgkin-Huxley mathematical model which describes the biophysics of the action potential – how they are generated and propagated and the modelling of action potential phases in terms of voltages and current variations. It is referred as a time continuous model which comprise of a set of non-linear differential equations to approximate the electrical characteristics of neurons (Hodgkin and Huxley, 1952).

The model is considered among the most biological realistic models as it captures accurately the complex features of real neurons. This naturally leads to the model possessing large numbers of highly non-linear variables and are mathematically hard to analyse. As a result, creating neural network simulations of Hodgkin-Huxley neurons are computationally expensive due to the number of parameters that are involved (~1200 FLOPS for 1ms simulation time per neuron (Izhikevich, 2004)).

Integrate and fire (IF) neurons

The roots of IF neurons were first proposed by Lapicque in 1907 (Brunel and van Rossum, 2007). This neuron model aims to model aspects of the Hodgkin Huxley model such as predicting the effects on membrane potential in response to input currents, generating spikes when membrane potential is above a threshold and repolarising from a reset voltage to resting membrane potential. To remain

biologically accurate, a ‘leaky’ aspect is added to the IF model to form the Leaky Integrate and Fire (LIF) model. A decay factor is added to mimic the diffusion of ions in a biological neuron. This model is a highly simplified model and is well suited for large scale simulations due to ~5 FLOPS required for 1ms of simulation time per neuron (Izhikevich, 2004). It is also accurate in generating spikes encoded temporally and is a valid model of spike generation in the soma (Gerstner, 2014). Figure 6 presents the LIF neuron equation (Izhikevich, 2004):

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = -\frac{v - v_{eq}}{\tau} + I(t)$$

Figure 6: the LIF neuron model equation (Gerstner, 2008).

The equation describes the membrane potential v with respect to time t . I is the input current as a function of time t , $\tau = RC$ is the membrane time constant time scale over which the neuron decays and v_{eq} is the resting potential.

The LIF neuron is said to only one state variable $\frac{dv}{dt}$ and cannot support more complex neuron dynamics.

Izhikevich (IZH) model

The Izhikevich model is an alternative neuron model proposed in 2003 by Izhikevich. The model attempts to compromise between the biological accuracy of the Hodgkin-Huxley model and the computational efficiency of LIF neurons (Izhikevich, 2003).

The Izhikevich model is represented in Figure 7 by the ordinary differential equations below obtained through bifurcation methodologies that reduce Hodgkin-Huxley models to a 2D set of ODEs.

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{v} &= 0.04v^2 + 5v + 140 - u + I \\ \dot{u} &= a(bv - u) \\ \text{if, } v &\geq +30mV, \text{ then } \begin{cases} v \leftarrow c \\ u \leftarrow u + d. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 7: Mathematical description of the Izhikevich neuron model (Izhikevich, 2003).

This model includes more variables which enables the exhibition of firing patterns of all cortical neurons. Its takes ~13 FLOPS for 1ms simulation time for each neuron to model more complex behaviour and provide a balance between biological plausibility and efficiency in simulations of large networks.

2.4.4 Modelling Synaptic Plasticity

Hebbian learning

The basic understanding of biological spike-timing dependent plasticity (STDP) presented has its roots in Hebbian theory which is a postulate put forward by Donald Hebb in his publication “The Organization of Behaviour”, first published in 1949.

The postulate that will be focused on is Hebbian learning, which is the idea that the synaptic connections between neurons are strengthened in proportion to the degree of correlation between pre and post synaptic activity. Hebb states "When an axon of cell A is near enough to excite B and repeatedly or persistently takes part in firing it, some growth process or metabolic change takes place in one or both cells such that A's efficiency, as one of the cells firing B, is increased" (Hebb, 1949, pg.62). Neuron A is more likely to fire in a way that makes neuron B fire. This proposal is referred to as the Hebb synapse and forms the basis of long term potentiation used in STDP.

There are two other postulates of Hebb's theory which are:

Cell assemblies – A collection of neurons that usually fire together. It is proposed that this is the basis of mental images or ideas represented as an assembly that tend to fire at the same time due to Hebbian learning. It has been studied that the firing patterns of neurons in the cell assemblies are 'remembered' after the original event that triggered them which forms a memory (Klein, 2011).

Phase sequence – Hebb proposed that the act of thinking is in fact a sequential activation of sets of cell assemblies to facilitate human actions. These actions are thought to be evoked by prior cell assemblies and sensory events. The discussed postulates form Hebbian theory that explains aspects of how the nervous system directs behaviour (Klein, 2011).

Spike timing Dependent plasticity STDP

STDP is considered a subset of Hebbian learning and builds upon Hebb's original hypothesis by factoring in a long term depression operation when the post synaptic neuron fires before the pre-synaptic neuron. This hypothesis forms our underlying beliefs on the strengthening on synapses over time as presented in "Biological synaptic plasticity".

Much experimentation has been focused around the examination of the correlation and relative timing between the pre and post synaptic spikes on a millisecond level. Markram (1997) demonstrated empirically Long Term Potentiation (LTP) and Long Term Depression LTD relative to the timing of pre and post synaptic action potentials. Landmark experiments to strengthen the credibility of STDP conducted by Bi and Poo (1998) known as the STDP function or learning window, plots the change in synaptic weight as a function of the timing of pre-post spike. Their experiments showed synapses were activated within 5-20ms before a post synaptic spike occurred for LTP and vice versa for LTD. These works helped to propel the credibility of the theory of STDP to its biological plausibility.

Figure 8: A summary of the STDP rule with a visualisation of the STDP function (Sjöström and Gerstner, 2010).

Figure 8 is a summary of the STDP rule with a visualisation of the STDP function that plots the degree of weight changes depending on the relative timings of pre and post spikes.

Synaptic trace

The trace value signifies the degree of change to be done to a weight and acts as a memory trace to keep track of the history of relative timing between pre and post synaptic action potentials.

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{Pre-synaptic trace} & \text{Post-synaptic trace} \\ \frac{dx_j}{dt} = -\frac{x_j}{\tau_x} + \sum_{t_j^f} \delta(t - t_j^f) & \frac{dy_i}{dt} = -\frac{y_i}{\tau_y} + \sum_{t_i^f} \delta(t - t_i^f) \end{array}$$

Figure 9: Pre and post synaptic trace equations (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

$\sum_{t_i^f} \delta(t - t_i^f)$ describes the increase in x_j due to spikes. x_j is the trace variable and $\frac{x_j}{\tau_x}$ describes how the neuron decreases over time according to the decay constant. Both of these variables describe the dynamics of the trace x .

Figure 10: (Top) a pre-synaptic spike generates a trace $x_j(t)$ to keep track of the firing time. This is read out when a post-synaptic occurs to determine the weight change. (Bottom) a post-synaptic spike generates a trace $y(t)$ which is read at a pre-synaptic spike (Sjöström and Gerstner, 2010).

Weight dependence

To replicate biological concepts, a window function is applied to each synapse in a simulated network. Usually two window functions are used, one to increase the weight by the trace value when the pre-synaptic neuron fires 5-20ms before the post synaptic neuron and another to decrease the weights otherwise.

Pre-synaptic weight update

$$\Delta w_{ij}^- = F_-(w_{ij})y_i(t_j^f)$$

Post-synaptic weight update

$$\Delta w_{ij}^+ = F_+(w_{ij})x_j(t_i^f)$$

Figure 11: Pre and post synaptic weight update equations (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

Figure 11 shows a pair of window functions to describe synaptic efficacy of pre and post synaptic neurons. The pre-synaptic weight update function changes the weight (w_{ij}) by an amount proportional to the post synaptic trace ($y_i(t_j^f)$). Similarly the post-synaptic weight function looks at the pre-synaptic trace $x_j(t)$ to update the weight.

A visualisation of the trace and window functions to update a synaptic connection between a pre and post neuron pair is presented below:

Figure 12: Weight changes over time (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

A graph plots the change in $w(t)$ over time as a pre and post neuron fires. The pre-neuron j and post neuron i are represented as spike trains. $x_j(t)$ is the pre-synaptic trace and $y_i(t)$ is the post synaptic trace, both are exponentially decaying functions of time. Whenever j spikes, the trace $x_j(t)$ increases and continues to decay, and similarly for i . Furthermore, whenever neuron j fires the weight decreases proportional the current value $y_i(t)$ and whenever neuron i fires, the weight increases proportional the current value $x_j(t)$.

2.5 Compartmental modelling

Up to this point neurons have been described as having a membrane potential consisting of a single variable for membrane potential and the spatial variation has been ignored. This is known as a single-compartment neuron where compartments are typically identified as possessing a local potential. Difficulties arise when researchers want to study the effects of membrane potential along the dendritic tree of a neuron. This is due to the fact that the charge inside the cell membrane does not exist only in one state. As the charge fluctuates in the membrane due to neuron inputs ion channels open to allow positive or negative ions into the membrane and initiate chemical reactions that propagate the membrane potential through dendritic trees towards the soma or through the axon away from the soma. Single compartments do not factor in this complexity.

To accommodate the modelling of dendritic behaviour the Cable Theory was applied to dendritic trees to create the Rall model (Rall, 2009), where dendritic trees can be separated into cylinders. Cable theory aims to describe how neuron inputs are propagated to the neuron soma. Equivalent circuits can be applied to the cylinders to represent the electrical properties of parts of a membrane. This combination of cable theory and equivalent circuits give rise to the following cable properties applicable to dendrites:

- Membrane resistance – The ability of charges (ions) to leak out of the membrane for repolarization
- Internal resistance – the ability of charges to spread through the cell nerve
- Membrane capacitance - the ability of the membrane to store charge

Figure 13: A cylinder that represents a section of the dendritic tree. The equivalent circuit inside the cylinder is an electrical representation of the cable model (Timofeeva, 2008).

A compartment is typically created by introducing a local membrane potential which defines the state space of the compartment. Depending on where the compartment is located, this allows the compartment to undertake more complex processing of neural signals based on how many membrane potentials it receives. Compartments allow neurons with varying dendritic structures to be modelled but simplifies interactions between branches. This concept enables multi-compartmental modelling.

Figure 14: A section of dendritic tree sectioned into cylinders (Gerstner, 2014).

Each cylinder represents a section of the membrane and forms a compartment I_{μ} refers to ions flowing into the membrane, $R_{\mu T}$ is the membrane resistance and R_L is the internal resistance (Gerstner, 2014).

2.6 Pyramidal neurons

Pyramidal neurons are an excitatory cell type and make up 70-80% of the cerebral cortex (Nieuwenhuys, 1994) which is the outer layer of tissue in the human brain that are used in advanced cognitive functions.

Figure 15: The structure of an L5 pyramidal neuron showing tuft, apical, and basal dendrites. Adapted from (Spruston, 2008).

Research into pyramidal neurons

This project is concerned with the functional properties of dendrites of L5 cortex neurons. There are issues with knowledge on pyramidal neurons where little is known of properties and functions of tuft dendrites in L5 cortex neuron spiking. Existing research conducted offers the notion that distal tuft dendrites could be more responsible for spike generation than previously thought (Larkum, 2013). Larkum demonstrates that calcium spike at distal dendrites can be detected by a burst pattern of 2-4 spikes at $\sim 200\text{Hz}$ at the soma and indicates that the bursts are a fundamental coding mechanism for cortical neurons.

An additional study investigated the function of tuft dendrites in processing synaptic input (Larkum et al., 2009). What was demonstrated was that different parts of the dendritic structure fire differently. In addition to the traditional sodium spike initiated at the soma, two additional spiking behaviours were observed by Larkum, a calcium apical spike that transmits signals from the apical tuft dendrite to the soma and NMDA spikes from compartments in the finer dendritic branches that interact in a non-linear way. This is visualised in Figure 16.

Figure 16: A pyramidal neuron model illustrating the three top-down spike initiation channels: initiation of NMDA spike at distal fine dendritic branches from compartments, calcium spikes initiated from the apical tuft and sodium spikes at the somatic compartment (Larkum et al., 2009).

For the objectives of this project, these studies provide adequate background knowledge and motivation to demonstrate these observations in neuromorphic hardware. As a first exploratory step, it is envisioned that a pyramidal neuron with two compartments will be implemented on SpiNNaker to mimic Figure 16. A compartment to represent the apical dendrite and another compartment to represent the basal dendrite to enable the modelling of the effects of calcium and sodium spikes. This will contribute to the EU Human Brain Project's ambition to develop a brain model that is more accurate to biological principles concerning the function of dendrites in L5 cortex neurons.

2.7 Dendritic learning in pyramidal neurons

Urbanczik and Senn (2014) propose a learning rule that uses a local dendritic potential as a third factor alongside pre and post spike timings to induce STDP. They present a compartmental model in which to demonstrate the viability of the learning rule for supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement learning paradigms. Urbanczik and Senn employ a simplified model compared to Larkum which dismisses the finer dendrites and just concentrates on the somatic and apical calcium spiking compartments. For the model that will be used in this project, will be based Urbanczik and Senn's model as it is a simplified version that still preserves the calcium based apical dendrite and a somatic compartment located at the basal dendrite.

Figure 17: A visual representation of the neuron model used as the basis of the learning rule where U is the somatic compartment (Urbanczik and Senn, 2014).

$\phi(U)$ represents the instantaneous firing rate of the somatic voltage as a sigmoidal function and V_w represents the dendritic compartment voltage. g_E and g_I provide time varying input to the soma. w_i represents synaptic strengths in the dendrite represented as a vector.

Dendritic prediction

The learning rule relies on a modulating voltage that is calculated as the difference between the somatic and dendritic potentials, known as the dendritic prediction error. Urbanczik and Senn assumes that $g_E = g_I = 0$ where the somatic compartment receives no input. Any current in the dendrite will be adopted by the soma in time. The rate $\phi(V_w)$ can be seen as a dendritic prediction of the somatic firing rate $\phi(U)$ where learning in the dendritic synapses is done by reducing the rate prediction error $\phi(U) - \phi(V_w)$.

This calculation is shown in the mathematical representation of the plasticity rule $PI_i(t)$ and describes the somatodendritic prediction error in response to a post synaptic potential:

$$PI_i(t) = (S(t) - \phi(V_w(t)))h(V_w(t))PSP_i(t)$$

Figure 18: The Urbanczik-Senn plasticity rule

$S(t)$ – represents the somatic spike train and records the actual spiking of the neuron

$\phi(V_w)$ – is the dendritic prediction of the somatic potential

$h(V_w(t))$ – is a constant that defines a positive weighting function

$PSP_i(t)$ – Is the Post-Synaptic-Potential evoked at the dendrite

This research provides additional theoretical support for the notion that tuft dendrites influence not only spiking but learning in pyramidal neurons. To the best of the author's knowledge little to no

study has been conducted to investigate the behaviour of Urbanczik-Senn plasticity on pyramidal neurons in simulations on neuromorphic hardware. The research conducted will form a first step to realising this in neuromorphic hardware. This knowledge will be relevant to inform and direct code changes required to the existing API architecture to recreate these key terms and calculations.

3.0 Technology Review

This chapter will detail the novel concept of the SpiNNaker project in terms of:

- Hardware architecture
- Programming model and system software
- sPyNNaker host based API architecture

The topics to be researched will be useful in establishing a full picture of the capabilities and limitations of SpiNNaker relevant to the project.

3.1 The SpiNNaker Project

The SpiNNaker (Spiking Neural Network Architecture) project is a parallel computing system whose purpose is to simulate spiking neural networks. It is the product of 25 years of work – 15 years since conception and 10 years in active development (Furber et al., 2014). The computing system was developed at Manchester University and is headed by Professor Steven Furber along with his team of academics and researchers.

SpiNNaker was built with two research questions in mind (Furber, 2015):

1. Can we harness the performance increases of computers and massively-parallel computing systems to quicken the pace of our understanding of brain function?
2. Can the increased understanding of how the brain functions be applied to create more fault-tolerant parallel computational systems?

In response to the above questions SpiNNaker was developed and the goal is to implement 1 million mobile phone processors (cores) in one computer and is able to model 1% of the human brain – or 10 mice brains. Currently the SpiNNaker system has 500,000 processors (Furber, 2016).

To underpin the construction of SpiNNaker, the following design principles were considered:

- **Virtualised topology**

In biology different parts of the Brain have different wiring structures. This means that SpiNNaker has to be re-wired in order to model different areas of the Brain. Therefore SpiNNaker maps problems by virtualising the topology between a problem graph describing the set of neurons to be modelled and a graph describing how the machine is built physically (BCS, 2015). This defines how architecture of the low level software framework and is further elaborated upon in 3.3.1 Topology Mapping and 3.3.2 Problem Mapping - A SpiNNaker parallel program.

- **Bounded asynchrony**

A big challenge for parallel computation is synchronisation – bringing all processors to the same point in the computation. As a result, SpiNNaker does not do this, but uses bounded asynchrony instead, where time models itself. This means that each processor has its own time and input/output operations happen as and when (BCS, 2015).

- **Energy frugality**

According to Furber, processors are essentially a free resource as the cost of implementing an ARM processor is relatively cheap (BCS, 2015). The real cost of computation is not buying the hardware but supplying the energy to run the system. SpiNNaker runs to 10^{-8} Joules per synaptic connection. In comparison, the human brain uses 10^{-14} Joules per synaptic connection – an order of six magnitudes more efficient than the current implementation of SpiNNaker (Furber, 2015).

3.1.1 The SpiNNaker neuromorphic chip

The SpiNNaker system consists of Nodes that contains two silicon dies – the chip itself and the 128M SDRAM gold wire bonded onto the SpiNNaker die. Each node system NoC (Network on chip) contains 18 processors (cores) that share the 128M of SDRAM (Furber et al., 2015).

Figure 19: Each 2d mesh represents a Spinnaker die. The darker shaded rectangle is the SDRAM while the gold square underneath is the SpiNNaker chip itself. (APT Advanced Processor Technologies Research Group¹, n.d.).

Each core possesses 64 kbytes of data tightly coupled memory (DTCM) and 32 kbytes of instruction tightly coupled memory (ITCM). The cores communicate with each other and memory using 5 or 9 byte packets transmitted by a routing sub system around the system (Furber et al., 2013).

Figure 20: A 48-node SpiNNaker board (Galluppi, 2013).

3.1.2 SpiNNaker advantages

Programming - A big advantage is that SpiNNaker is programmable in a digital way using C code. This allows shortcomings in hardware to be implemented in code and differs from other neuromorphic platforms that result solely on analogue circuits.

Openly accessibility – as of mid-2015 the Manchester machine is open for non-expert use, where application developers can assess the machine’s resources through the internet by using the HBP Collaboratory Portal (Services.humanbrainproject.eu, n.d.).

Run time architecture - SpiNNaker is able to run in biological real-time due to the speed at which a node’s routers can communicate with other nodes. This is the main differentiator between the SpiNNaker system and other neuromorphic hardware. This enables the system to be more realistic to biology when emulating spiking neural networks.

3.1.3 SpiNNaker limitations

Scope - Perhaps a limitation of the system is that it is not a general purpose machine as memory constraints prevent conventional operating systems from running. Problems are required to be broken down into small and simple functions where the connectivity describing how the functions link together are static or at most slowly changing (BCS, 2015).

Hardware limits – On chip memory is very limited 96 bytes in total. Therefore more complex operations involving synapses are done by storing synapse information of the 128m SDRAM and neuron information is held in local memory (Furber et al., 2013). Direct Memory Access (DMA) transfers are initiated in software to transfer parameters between node memory and SDRAM to achieve neuron and synapse operations.

Arithmetic limits - The SpiNNaker ARM968 chip possesses no floating point hardware support. Instead ‘soft’ floating point can be emulated in software which is slow and consumes memory. Fixed point uses integer operations which sacrifices precision to maintain speed and performance (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

Packet limitations - the asynchronous nature of the communications system on SpiNNaker means that packets containing spike information from neurons may sometimes be dropped to avoid a communications deadlock. A reinjector mechanism to re-send the spike has been developed as a safeguard (Spinnakermanchester.github.io, n.d.).

3.2 Hardware overview

The following is an overview of the hardware and software technology of SpiNNaker.

3.2.1 The SpiNNaker Hardware Architecture

The below figure presents the internals of a SpiNNaker node with each of its 18 cores. Each node communicates with other nodes via 6 bidirectional inter-chip links and each link can transport up to 6 million spikes per second – a pre-requisite for conducting spiking-based neural network simulation.

Figure 21: A SpiNNaker die (Furber et al., 2013)

An individual core the black grid depicts the data memory (32kb of code space) in which a neural modelling code resides. This memory is split into two sections (Furber et al., 2013):

1. The instruction memory which contains the run-time kernel code and application callbacks.
2. Data memory – contains state data of the kernel and neurons along with the stack and heap.

Underneath the data memory is the processor itself which comprises a core. This is an ARM968 which Figure 22 presents. Some notable features are the tightly coupled core local memories which are directly connected to the processor and accessible at the processors clock speed (Furber et al., 2013).

Figure 22: The ARM968 subsystem (Furber et al., 2013).

The Advanced High Speed Bus (AHB) master interface runs at the full processor clock rate and connects all memory locations to the processor as shown in Figure 22. As a result this gives the

processor direct access to the memory registers of the DMA (Direct Memory Access), communications and timer/interrupt controllers. This provides a path to the node through the DMA controller and gives the processor access to memory and resources provided by the node. The RAM port is the connection to the SDRAM and is where the synaptic connectivity data resides (Furber et al., 2013).

3.2.2 Address Event Representation (AER)

AER could be considered the basis of the SpiNNaker execution model (Furber et al., 2013). The underlying principle refers to a neuron firing a spike being a pure asynchronous event where the destination of a spike only receives (Furber et al., 2013):

- The time of the spike.
- The Identity (“address”) of the spiking neuron.

Time models itself in a real time system so when a neuron spikes, its identity is broadcasted. Packet switched communication is used to implement AER where spikes are represented as multi-cast packets. This comes with some latency but this is under the standard biological time latency that biological neurons have so this has no effect (Furber et al., 2013).

3.2.3 Point neuron Model

SpiNNaker is optimised for the point neuron model, which is known for abstracting away the dendritic structure and enables all inputs to be applied directly to the soma. The synaptic inputs are summed to form the total soma input that is used in differential equations to compute membrane voltage and spiking occurrence (Furber et al., 2013).

3.2.4 The Routing Sub-system

The router representing the routing subsystem is the heart of SpiNNaker, giving the system the capability of running real-time neural network models which are currently infeasible on a conventional computer due to its deterministic nature (HBP Neuromorphic Computing Platform, 2016). The router folds the routing tables needed for spike packet routing and system communications.

Essentially the router is similar to a conventional packet switching mechanism found on traditional packet switchers. However, in SpiNNaker the system is condensed down into a few millimetres. Thus, the SpiNNaker system can be viewed as a ‘mini-internet’ with conventional routing protocols:

- Multi-cast (MC)
- P2P (point-to-point)
- NN (Nearest neighbor)
- FR (fixed route)

Figure 23: Routing architecture and links between SpiNNaker nodes (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

3.2.5 The SpiNNaker Datagram Protocol (SDP)

The SpiNNaker Datagram protocol is used for transferring data in SpiNNaker and are embedded in the conventional routing protocols used in SpiNNaker. When SDP packets are sent between nodes they are embedded in point-to-point packets. When communicated over the internet they are encapsulated within UDP packets (Temple, 2011). For the purposes of the of the project it is sufficient to know that system API's use SDP packets to move data blocks in SpiNNaker.

3.2.6 The Vectored Interrupt Controller (VIC)

Each processor core possesses a vectored interrupt controller that enables and disables interrupts from various sources and to wake the processor from it default sleep state as part of SpiNNaker's event driven operating mode (Furber et al., 2013).

It is shown in Figure 24 and the controller's purpose is to manage both standard interrupts (IRQ) and fast interrupts (FIQ) along with indicating the active interrupt sources of IRQ for vectoring purposes. The following can be sources of interrupts on SpiNNaker (Furber et al., 2013):

- Communication controller flow-control
- DMA complete/error/time-out
- Timers (& watchdog timer)
- An Interrupt from another processor on the SpiNNaker die shown in Figure 21
- A routing packet-error
- System fault
- Ethernet controller
- Off-chip signals
- 32-kHz slow system clock
- Software interrupt, for downgrading FIQ to IRQ.

3.2.7 Event-driven execution model

Since hardware constraints prevent conventional operating systems to run on each core, SpiNNaker is designed to be entirely interrupt-driven (Furber et al., 2013). SpiNNaker operations are essentially a series of choreographed interrupts with a low-level "service provision" system running on each core which follows an event driven model. The processor wakes up from its default sleep state, handles an event and returns to sleep again to maintain energy frugality. This is the execution model shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24: The event driven software model (Furber et al., 2013).

The model can be broken down into 3 distinct events (Sharman, 2013):

1. Incoming Packet Event
2. Direct Memory Access (DMA) completion event
3. Timer tick event

Incoming packet event from a location in the SpiNNaker machine

In the first event, a packet event represents an interrupt which is usually a spike and the processor core awakes to handle it. This involves the core finding the necessary data structures to handle the spike. These are the data structures are placed onto the SDRAM chip. During this process, the packet buffer fills up but does not wait for packets until it is full to trigger a Direct Memory Access (DMA) transfer. The processor then returns to sleep, waiting for the DMA transfer to complete (Sharman, 2013).

DMA transfer completion

This marks the second event, in which the DMA initiated from the first event completes and wakes the processor up again. It proceeds to process all the synapse data and updates the status of all neurons locally if there have been any changes (ie: synaptic weight changes from neuron spikes). After this, the processor returns to sleep (Sharman, 2013).

Timer tick

The third event independent from the other two is the timer tick event. This is where every one millisecond the processor wakes up and runs the neuron model programs that have been uploaded to the SpiNNaker board - which are typically differential equation solvers. Some neurons may issue spikes during the solving phase, after which the processor returns to sleep. These events require scheduling which is described further in 3.3.6 SpiNNaker Application Runtime Kernel (SARK) (Sharman, 2013).

Figure 26: The “anatomy” of a SpiNNaker Parallel program (Furber et al., 2015).

3.3.3 Application Programming Model – System software

The software on the SpiNNaker machine follows an event driven model and can be divided into control software and application software. The following are key components to the application programming model:

1. The SpiNNaker Control and Monitor Program (SC&MP) – Low level control software
2. The SpiNNaker Application Runtime Kernel (SARK) – application software
3. The SpiNNaker API – Spin1

3.3.4 Programming languages

The programming languages to develop and run applications on SpiNNaker are:

- C
- Python

The role of C

The role of the C code is to describe the algorithms and define the executables of a neuron model/ computational load of neurons. This includes the neuron executable, changing state and spike firing.

The C code does not contain the parameters needed for the neuron model to function, such as the resting membrane voltage value. These parameters are the responsibility of Python and PyNN (Davison, 2008) and are given via a PyNN script. In most cases C code will be solving an ODE (Ordinary differential equation). An ODE describes the change in how a neuron responds to input over time. Most of the system software is written primarily in C to achieve good performance despite system memory constraints.

C data structures and parameters

The parameters and state of a neuron at any point in time needs to be stored in memory. For each neuron, the C header files define ordering and size of each stored value. The C types can be standard integer and floating-point or ISO draft standard fixed point. There is one global data structure which

services all neurons on the core (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016). This is useful to know for programming any mathematical operations in C executable programs.

The role of python

Python determines the number of neurons needed, the number of nodes needed and the “start point” of the application and the infrastructures required. In short, python code interfaces to SpiNNaker hardware from the host machine, packaging the C executable to be able to run on a SpiNNaker board.

3.3.5 The SpiNNaker Control and Monitor Program (SC&MP)

SC&MP runs continuously on the core selected as the monitor processor and its primary function is to allow applications to be loaded onto the 16/17 application cores on each node. The software also facilitates routing of SDP packets allowing bidirectional sending and receiving of packets nodes (Furber et al., 2014). It is used as part of booting the machine when uploading programs.

3.3.6 SpiNNaker Application Runtime Kernel (SARK)

SARK primarily controls the flow of execution by scheduling and dispatching application call back functions and creating a runtime environment (Apt.cs.manchester.ac.uk, n.d.). It also handles memory management and interrupt control and maintains a communications interface with SC&MP which allows the application to communicate with and be controlled by other SpiNNaker nodes (Furber et al., 2014).

The programming model operates on the principle that applications can’t control execution flow but only indicate which functions (callbacks) should be executed. The underlying motivation for this set up is to maintain energy frugality, where the cores of the SpiNNaker processor are kept in a low power state and only respond to ‘interesting’ events (Furber et al., 2014). Examples of such events are described in 3.2.6 The Vectored Interrupt Controller (VIC) - namely when a packet containing a neuron spike is received by a SpiNNaker processor, A DMA transfer is completed or a timer tick event (Furber et al., 2014).

Figure 27: The application programming model. “CB queues refer to Callback queues” (APT Advanced Processor Technologies Research Group², n.d.)

These events require scheduling, so underpinning the software model is a real-time operating system which recognises 2 classes of events (Sharman, 2013):

- Queueable events
- Non-queueable events

The event queue is handled in priority order where during a delay of every one millisecond timestep, the processor keeps a queue of tasks to complete and repeats the processing of tasks before returning to sleep (Sharman, 2013).

Figure 27 presents the basic architecture to support the event driven framework where application developers write functions (call back routines) to handle packet, DMA and timer events which are registered with a particular priority at the kernel level. When an event occurs, the scheduler thread shown in Figure 27 either executes the call-back routine associated with the event immediately or is atomically executed if the call-back is non-queueable. Otherwise the scheduler places a queueable call-back into a scheduling queue on the dispatcher thread according to its priority in descending order. When a call-back is completed, control is returned to the dispatcher and the next highest priority call-back is executed (Furber et al., 2014).

It is important to note that queueable call-backs don't always execute as a single, non split-able atomic operation visible to other threads. A higher priority non-queueable call-back could take its place and execute if an associated event happens during execution of the queueable call-back. For example this could be a neuron spike that generates a packet event. The dispatcher returns to a sleep state where the processor core clock is switched off and waits for interrupts when the call-back queues are empty. It will wake up again if any event occurs (Furber et al., 2014).

3.3.7 SpiNNaker Application Programming Interface (SpiNNaker API)

While SARK provides the runtime environment, the event management library known as the Spin1 API provides an execution environment and manages the interrupt subsystem. This API sits between the underlying hardware and the user's application (Furber et al., 2014).

The SpiNNaker API provides functions to support the programming model and handle callbacks by controlling entry and exit from critical operations. This is to prevent a higher priority call back causing an interrupt during critical system operations such as such as reading synaptic data from the shared SDRAM memory (Furber et al., 2014).

3.4 Application Programming Model – Host software

A "host" refers to a computer that controls a SpiNNaker system. Host software tools allows application I/O from the host machine to control the spinnaker system and to upload applications onto the system board. This section will detail a selection of the host API's relevant for the project domain.

A number of SDP-based API's have been developed written in the above languages for application developers to use and are outlined below:

3.4.1 Ybug

Ybug provides a CLI to load programs onto the system and provides commands to specify how to program should run. For example, the command, loads the program on core 1 with an application id of 14. SARK, SC&MP, Spin1 api and ybug are packaged up into the "spinnaker_tools" API.

```
app_load test.aplx . 1 14
```

Figure 28: ybug code to load a program onto one core.

3.4.2 PACMAN

PACMAN configures the parallel operating nature of SpiNNaker and shared the model across resources (processors, SDRAM and router). It is essentially a set of algorithms used to translate a neural network model into machine executable code to run on SpiNNaker (Furber et al., 2014). The data that the algorithms use represent the neural network model, system information and methods for data structure translation. Figure 30 presents the algorithm top-down sequence of algorithms used to process the model (starting from “Partitioning”) and the data representations that are created by the algorithms (starting from “Model View”). It is directly involved in the problem mapping process described in 3.3.1 Topology Mapping and 3.3.2 Problem Mapping - A SpiNNaker parallel program and translates the problem graph into an abstract topology model based on the populations (set of neurons) and projections (connections between them) with the help of the GraphFrontEnd software API and PyNN language. This new model is based on edges and vertices which will be elaborated upon when describing the GraphFrontEnd API. Figure 30 presents this as the “Model View”.

Users interact with the PACMAN platform through neural languages, one of which is called PyNN (Python Neural Networks) (Davison, 2008).

PACMAN configures SpiNNaker’s parallel computing structure in the following ways:

Partitioning

The populations are split but the projections are preserved according the resources offered by processors at the time, depending on the neural and synaptic capacity of each core. This creates a sub-graph, whose sub-vertices are to be mapped or routed and sub edges that join the vertices together (Furber et al., 2014).

Mapping/Routing

The model is represented in a directional graph shown in Figure 30. The graph is then mapped by the placement of a subgraph on a node in accordance to the resources provided by a node such that the sub-vertices placed onto a node does not exceed its capability.

It is then routed onto a physical machine instance creating the system view (machine graph) using the system library (Furber et al., 2014). This is achieved through (Pacman.readthedocs.io, n.d.):

- The creation of multicast routing information – assigning routing key/mask pairs to sub-edges of the particular sub-graph
- Allocation of the key/mask pairs to a subgraph – this idea being each sub-vertex broadcasts packets with distinct combinations

Figure 29: A PACMAN graph with edges (E1 -4)and vertices (V1-4) (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

- Routing of sub-edges between sub-vertices using the routing keys and masks. This creates routing tables to facilitate the routing subsystem on a hardware level. Accurate data is transmitted along the specified edge when requested.

This process generates simulation data to be run on the SpiNNaker system board. Multicast packets is used in this instance since this packet type conveys spiking information from the source neuron.

Translating

The whole model is translated using mechanisms stored in the model library into machine-executable code for ARM cores, SDRAM and routers (Furber et al., 2014). This creates a binary image containing information of synaptic weights, the machine executable neural modelling code and routing tables information.

Loading/Executing

The model is loaded onto the system and executed through the use of other host software detailed below. Other host software that help PACMAN achieve this are described below.

Figure 30: PACMAN algorithm flow (left) and the data representations that are developed (Furber, 2015).

3.4.3 Data Specification

The Data Specification module is used to write the data for each sub vertex by creating a memory image via the Data Specification language file (Dataspecification.readthedocs.io, n.d.).

This is the main usage of the python code as this performs a “hand-shaking” process between C and Python on the location and method of storing neuron parameters in the SDRAM of SpiNNaker. This is hidden in the PyNN code via interfaces and requires a PyNN model to be constructed.

3.4.5 SpiNNMan

SpiNNMan is used to communicate with the SpiNNaker board, send and receive packets in a range of SpiNNaker formats and load the data onto the machine along with the binary executable code generated by PACMAN (Spinman.readthedocs.io, n.d.).

3.4.6 GraphFrontEnd (GFE)

The GFE serves two main purposes, computation and communication. It aids PACMAN by facilitating the representation of the problem graph into a machine graph (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

3.5 sPyNNaker API overview

This section will be a continuation of host-based API's for Spinnaker. A focused overview of the current implementation of the host based API sPyNNaker will detail the most important API aspects and files relevant to achieve the project outcomes.

3.5.1 The PyNN API

PyNN (Python Neural Networks) is an API which is a language based on the Python programming language used to model neural networks. PyNN provides a library of standard neuron, synapse and synaptic plasticity models which can be modelled with the use of a simulator backend.

Some examples of simulation environments include NEURON (NEURON, 2014), developed by Yale university to facilitate the running of neural simulations. Other examples include BRIAN (Goodman, 2009), another open source simulator written in python used to simulate neural networks or individual neurons. The third simulator that PyNN supports is NEST (Nest-simulator.org, n.d.), which focuses on large clusters of neurons and looks at the dynamics, size and structure rather than the intricate details of individual neurons.

Since biologically accurately neural modelling of neural networks is currently very computationally expensive PyNN abstracts modelling to a high level, which involve sets of neurons called populations, layers, columns and their connections which are called projections.

3.5.2 The sPyNNaker API

The SPyNNaker API is the main interface between the host and the SpiNNaker system used to run neural simulations. It is designed exclusively for the SpiNNaker system and due to the various hardware constraints, such as processor count and on-board memory, a subset of the PyNN 0.7 API is currently implemented (Spinnakermanchester.github.io, n.d.).

Therefore, the sPyNNaker API uses the same neural modelling concepts such as neuron populations and the connections between them (Projections).

3.5.3 Required code separation

The crucial difference between PyNN and sPyNNaker is platform independence. The sPyNNaker API includes C and custom python code that is exclusive for SpiNNaker as well as PyNN code. The API utilises C and python code to deliver neural modelling. C is used to achieve high performance on hardware-constrained devices such as the SpiNNaker system board and makes the C executable – a binary file of the neuron model to be simulated.

The python code provides an “infrastructure” in the form of parameter values and input values to configure the setup and load phases. C executables to be run on the system board can be packaged

Figure 31: The software architecture for SpiNNaker depicting the position of the PyNN language in the context of the overall software architecture (Jin et al., 2010).

up and uploaded and provide neural parameters in a format that the C code of the API can understand. This concerns an agreed location in SDRAM to store the PyNN parameters that can be accessed by C code in simulations ran on the SpiNNaker system.

Figure 32: A visualisation of code separation between C and Python (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

In Figure 32 Network description refers to the python code and Binary Image represents the C executable. The PARTition and Configuration MANager (PACMAN) maps neurons to cores and generates routing tables for spike transmission depending on the connectivity of the network. These instructions are then written to the Binary Image (C executable) to be placed in the different memory locations on the SpiNNaker node.

3.5.4 sPyNNaker API key features

This section will briefly detail the main features of the sPyNNaker API.

3.5.4.1 Neuron models

The following subset of PyNN modules for neuron modelling components are implemented in sPyNNaker:

Neuron build	Input type	Neuron model	Synapse type
IFCurrExp	Current based	Leaky Integrate and fire	Exponential
IFCondExp	Conductance based	Leaky Integrate and fire	Exponential
IFCurrDualExp	Current based	Leaky Integrate and fire	Dual Exponential
IZKCurrExp	Current based	Izhikevich	Exponential
IZKCondExp	Conductance based	Izhikevich	Exponential

Synapse types implemented by sPyNNaker

Exponential synapses - Exponential synapses include one excitatory and an inhibitory synapse type per neuron which decay exponentially with a configured time constant. Each synapse type has a ring and input buffer.

Dual-excitatory synapses - Dual-excitatory synapses include two separate excitatory synapses and one inhibitory synapse per neuron also with an exponential decay. Each synapse type has a ring and input buffer.

Input types implemented by sPyNNaker – current and conductance based inputs are implemented

Threshold types – the threshold potential is implemented as a hard coded value.

Synaptic Plasticity – A slow model of STDP is only supported that is implemented by two timing dependence rules: SpikePairRule and PfisterSpikeTripletRule. The weight dependence rules that are implemented are AdditiveWeightDepdence and MultiplicativeWeightDepdence.

External input – sPyNNaker supports two models that can be used for spike injection:

1. SpikeSourceArray – applies a predefined set of spikes times.
2. SpikeSourcePoisson – applies a randomly generated set of spikes from a Poisson distribution.

Figure 33: A visual representation of the C code API files in sPyNNaker (Stokes, 2015).

3.5.5 Creating and running neuron models on SpiNNaker

Any neuron model requires both C and python code, these are separate but must be perfectly coordinated (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

The following components can be used to create a complete working neuron model:

1. **Input type** - specifies whether the input is current or conductance based.
2. **Synapse type** - specifies the synapse type to be used

3. **Threshold type** – this specifies a hardcoded threshold value
4. **Additional input** - component additional input based on membrane voltage only implemented in SpyNNakerExtraModelsPlugin API
5. **Neuron Model** – describes how membrane voltage changes over time.
6. **Synapse dynamics** – specifies the activation of STDP

A model that possesses these components is called a build. Each build has a make file that compiles into an '.aplx' executable file to be run on SpiNNaker. This contains information about the neural parameter definitions and instructions concerning the configuration of synaptic weights and routing tables on the SpiNNaker system board (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

Below is an example of a make file for a neuron build:

```

1 APP = $(notdir $(CURDIR))
2 BUILD_DIR = build/
3
4 NEURON_MODEL = $(EXTRA_SRC_DIR)/neuron/models/my_neuron_model_impl.c
5 NEURON_MODEL_H = $(EXTRA_SRC_DIR)/neuron/models/my_neuron_model_impl.h
6 INPUT_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/input_types/input_type_current.h
7 THRESHOLD_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/threshold_types/threshold_type_static.h
8 SYNAPSE_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/synapse_types/synapse_types_exponential_impl.h
9 SYNAPSE_DYNAMICS = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/plasticity/synapse_dynamics_static_impl.c
10
11 include ../Makefile.common

```

Figure 34: An example of a neuron build make file (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

An important feature is the name and location of the built model. This is specified in line 1 and 2 to be the name of the directory containing the make file and the build/ directory. The location of the directory is specified in the Makefile.common. Input type, synapse type and threshold type are all implemented in header files. The neuron model component is split into a header file which defined the neuron parameters and a C file that implements functionality. Line 11 references the makefile that is the next level up to inform the compiler of the location of the rest of the code to be linked. This produces an executable file placed in sPyNNaker\spynaker\pyNN\model_binaries to be used in python simulations (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

Notable API functions

API aspects relevant to this project include areas from the neuron model and synapse type components:

Neuron model component

Main data structure

The main neuron data structure `neuron_t` includes the state parameters of a single neuron. Common parameters that can be found in every neuron implementation include the membrane voltage and an offset input current. This is implemented as a struct mainly for performance reasons as a method of placing a list of variables under one name in a memory block to be accessed by a single pointer. Figure 35 is an example from `neuron_model_lif_impl.h`:

```

typedef struct neuron_t {
    // membrane voltage [mV]
    REAL V_membrane;

    // membrane resting voltage [mV]
    REAL V_rest;

    // membrane resistance [MOhm]
    REAL R_membrane;

    // 'fixed' computation parameter - time constant multiplier for
    // closed-form solution
    // exp( -(machine time step in ms)/(R * C) ) [...]
    REAL exp_TC;

    // offset current [nA]
    REAL I_offset;

    // countdown to end of next refractory period [timesteps]
    int32_t refract_timer;

    // post-spike reset membrane voltage [mV]
    REAL V_reset;

    // refractory time of neuron [timesteps]
    int32_t T_refract;
} neuron_t;

```

Figure 35: State parameters of a neuron defined in a struct (Rowley¹, 2015)

There is a global parameters data structure that holds parameters that should be shared across the whole population of neurons. This is useful if a network needed to use the same machine time step for example.

Updating the neuron state

This could be considered the main purpose of a neuron model. It takes the total excitatory and inhibitory inputs from the synapse type, along with an external bias to compute and return the new membrane voltage for the current time step. The external bias is considered to be an additional current that is used to drive the current closer to the threshold or away from it.

```
state_t neuron_model_state_update(  
    input_t exc_input, input_t inh_input, input_t external_bias, neuron_pointer_t  
    neuron);
```

Figure 36: The neuron state update function for membrane voltage (Rowley, 2015²).

Synapse type component

Another key neuron model component relevant to this project are synapse types. In the sPyNNaker API the dendritic operation is emulated with the use of a ring and input buffer which is possessed by each synapse. When a spike is received by the synapse a synaptic word is put into the ring buffer which acts as a delay between the synapse and the neuron. The ring buffer holds a synaptic weight and the input buffer holds a shaped weight input that is converted into an input. The ring buffer holds 16 elements to enable a synapse to have a delay between 1 and 16 time steps to emulate a dendritic delay analogous to biological principles. The element at the front of the ring is taken at each time step, and placed in the input buffer to be shaped into an input to be received by the neuron.

Figure 37: Ring and input buffers of an excitatory synapse type. The ring buffer has 16 slots and the input buffer contains one slot that the front element of the ring buffer is placed in at each time step.

Synapse data structure

Each synapse type header file defines a struct of type `synapse_param_t` that hold variables defining that are used as parameters for shaping the synaptic input. For example, the following is a struct for the “`synapse_types_dual_excitatory_exponential_impl.h`”:

```
typedef struct synapse_param_t {  
    decay_t exc_decay;  
    decay_t exc_init;  
    decay_t exc2_decay;  
    decay_t exc2_init;  
    decay_t inh_decay;  
    decay_t inh_init;  
} synapse_param_t;
```

Figure 38: Synapse parameters structure (Stokes and Rowley¹, 2017).

The struct includes parameters to compute and hold an initial weight value (exc_init, inh_init, exc2_init) that will be added to the input buffer when a spike occurs from a preceding neuron.

Synapse input shaping

The shaping functions add a decay to the existing element inside the input buffers. The ring buffer index is obtained for the current time to make sure the right neuron and synapse type is being updated. Then the conversion takes place to put the synaptic weight into the input buffers based on the rule specified by the synapse type.

```
Static void synapse_types_shape_input(input_t *input_buffers, index_t neuron_index, synapse_param_t* parameters);
```

Figure 39: API function to shape synaptic input. Source code from (Stokes and Rowley², 2017).

The method shapes the values in the input buffers for the synapse type of a neuron by calling the method `synapse_types_get_input_buffer_index` from `synapse_types.h` to return the index position in the input buffer that stores a synapse type for a neuron simulation. The index will also contain the location of the spikes that are of a specified synapse type (excitatory or inhibitory) that will be used to stimulate the neuron. Then a decay is added to the elements in the input buffer to mimic the valve-like behaviour of a synapse in biology along with the 'leaky' aspect of a neuron. The `synapse_param_t` parameters are extracted from SDRAM to initialise which synapse shaping rules to use.

Adding and retrieving inputs

Figure 40 shows the method that adds the synaptic weight inputs that are in the ring buffer into the input buffer after a spike is received by the neuron to be converted into current inputs by the `input_type`.

```
Static void synapse_types_add_neuron_input(input_t *input_buffers, index_t synapse_type_index, index_t neuron_index, synapse_param_t* parameters, input_t input)
```

Figure 40: Function add input to input buffer with decay (Stokes and Rowley², 2017)

Additional methods are implemented in the synapse type to retrieve the shaped value in the input buffer of each synapse. Figure shows an example of the obtain inputs from the excitatory buffer; a similar function for the inhibitory synapse is implemented.

```
static input_t synapse_types_get_excitatory_input(input_t *input_buffers, index_t neuron_index)
```

Figure 41: Function to get the input current from the excitatory input buffer (Stokes and Rowley², 2017)

Python code

Once the C code has been constructed into a neuron build, a corresponding PyNN model must be built to translate PyNN parameter values into c-readable form. This is done by creating a component

for each of the C components. The python components mainly consist of accessor and setter methods along with initialiser methods.

Python model builds

Another vital component is a python model build which are files that combine the python components in figure. This is where neuron parameters are assigned values. The components are initialised and passed to the AbstractPopulationVertex interface object that every neuron model needs to extend.

Figure 42: Python build hierarchy

Figure: A visualisation of the python build file including the required components. Additional input omitted as it is optional and can only be used in conjunction with SpyNNakerExtraModelsPlugin. synapse dynamics is implemented in its own build file SynapseDynamicsSTDP which extends “AbstractPlasticSynapseDynamics”.

The initialiser for AbstractPopulationVertex is where the python components of the neuron models are passed in as parameters along with the binary C executable and other parameters describing the network. This is used to inform PACMAN when configuring the topology graph to map the network onto SpiNNaker.

PyNN network description

This section will detail some of the most important features that form a PyNN network description to run simulations. A requirement of any simulation is to import the sPyNNaker API and any other Python modules to be used such as pylab which is part of the Matplotlib library to plot graphs.

```
import pylab
import pyNN.spiNNaker as sim
```

Next, any parameters for the simulation are defined. These can include the run time of the simulation and the timestep among others. The simulation is setup using these parameters.

```
run_time = 1000 # Set the run time of the execution
time_step = 1.0 # Set the time step of the simulation in milliseconds
n_neurons = 1 # Set the number of neurons to simulate
i_offset = 0.0 # Set the i_offset current
weight = 2.0 # Set the weight of input spikes
spike_times = range(0, run_time, 100) # Set the times at which to input a spike

sim.setup(timestep, min_delay=1.0, max_delay=10.0) # SpiNNaker Setup
```

The neuron model to be used and its properties are defined. These parameters must match those found in the python description of the model. Here, a current based Leaky-Integrate-and-Fire neuron is used with exponential decaying synapses.

```
model = sim.IF_curr_exp

cell_params = {'cm': 0.20, 'i_offset': 0.0, 'tau_m': 20.0, 'tau_refrac': 2.0,
               'tau_syn_E': 7.0, 'tau_syn_I': 7.0, 'v_reset': -70.0, 'v_rest': -65.0,
               'v_thresh': -50.0}
```

Sets of neurons are defined as a population. In this example, an input population is defined (input_pop) to provide external stimulation to the target population (population). A spike source array is used with a spike timing of 1 spike per 100 milliseconds (ms) as defined previously. A population of 40 IF_curr_exp neurons are defined.

```
input_pop = p.Population(40, p.SpikeSourceArray, {"spike_times":spike_times},
                                                    label="input")
population = sim.Population(40, model, cell_params)
```

Populations are connected using a projection. A connector object is defined to enable this which define weights and delays. The 'target' attribute specifies a target synapse to direct inputs to. The basic network has now been constructed.

```
connector = sim.OneToOneConnector(weights=3.0)
sim.Projection(input_pop, population , connector, target='excitatory')
```

Recording of neuronal properties such as membrane potential and spike activity can be set up so that it can be plotted after the simulation. To upload the network description, neuron model and parameters to SpiNNaker the run() method is used. When the simulation has finished, the results are communicated with the host machine for visualisation. It is important to note that a limitation of sPyNNaker is lack for any changing of weights, delays or neuron parameters during a simulation.

```
population.record_v() # Record neurons potentials
population.record() # Record spikes
sim.run(simtime) # Run simulation
```

Running a model in on SpiNNaker

The PyNN network description is the file that is run to set up the populations of neurons. The PACMAN host API module is used to partition the populations into sub populations according to the specified max atoms per core of the model and required resources for the synaptic matrix and Data specification writes the data for each subpopulation. SpiNNMan loads the parameters in the SDRAM onto the machine as well as the binary '.aplx' executable (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

Figure 43: How the host-based APIs interact when uploading neural simulation code onto the SpiNNaker system board (Sixth SpiNNaker Workshop, 2016).

3.5.6 Running neural simulations on SpiNNaker

A number of supporting API files are used in order to facilitate the successful operation of important processes for neural modelling. The following is an examination of the most important processes for this project.

The following describes the key files that enable time-driven neuron simulations.

Neuron.c

This API component is a key interface of a neuron model and provides functionality to initialise and update the neuron state at each time step, which is every 1 millisecond is used to stay consistent the standard biological delays used when modelling neurons (Sharman, 2013)

Void neuron_do_time_step_update()

This could be perhaps, the main function in this file which defines how the neural parameters are updated after a timer tick value of the processor. This happens in six key steps:

1. Obtain current membrane voltage of the neuron model
2. Retrieve the excitatory and inhibitory input values from the synapse type
3. Invoke the input_type implementation to convert a synaptic input from the input buffer into current value for both an excitatory and inhibitory input
4. Pass the current values to the neuron_model_state_update() function along with any external bias and the neuron parameters.
5. Invoke the threshold type implementation to determine if the neuron has spiked.
6. Let the neuron model know that it has spiked by calling the neuron_model_has_spiked(neuron_pointer_t neuron) method and passing in the struct that holds all the now-updated neuron parameters.

The routine also records neuron state, neuron inputs and any spikes that have occurred in the timestep if needed.

The following are important files detailing the functionality of synapse types in neuron processing.

Synapse_row.h

The API file is important to form the processing of synaptic rows. This is an address held in the SDRAM memory of the SpiNNaker board that contains a synaptic word 32-bits long that is created when a spike event occurs. This is illustrated below:

Weight	Delay	Synapse type	Neuron index
Synapse weight bits	Synapse delay bits	Synapse type bits	Synapse index bits (neuron ID)
		Synapse type index bits (the number of bits the synapse type needs and includes neuron ID size)	

Figure 44: A synaptic row

This file defines the data structure layout of the rows and specifies the number of bits each part of the word is allocated.

There are two functional types of synapses in sPyNNaker, fixed and plastic synapses. Fixed synapses don't have the infrastructure to support STDP learning but plastic synapses do. There is a synapse row for plastic and fixed synapses and this is used to process synapses to enable synaptic weight changes.

spike_processing.c

In this file the dynamic memory allocation controller starts a DMA transfer to reads the synaptic row and puts it into a DMA buffer. The file is also controls how spikes are processing by initiating key DMA transfers to fulfil the event driven model.

Synapses.c

Apart from the important function of initialising the synapse, Synapses.c is also responsible for processing the synaptic row and updating the ring and input buffers and is the primary handler for synaptic weights.

Updating the Ring buffers

It does this by extracting components such as the delay, ID and weight bits from the synaptic word and combining these components and converting them into a ring buffer offset. An int weight value is added to this offset which is held in the synapse weight bits and added to the ring buffer.

```

for (; fixed_synapse > 0; fixed_synapse--) {
    // Get the next 32 bit word from the synaptic_row
    // (should auto increment pointer in single instruction)
    uint32_t synaptic_word = *synaptic_words++;

    // Extract components from this word
    uint32_t delay = synapse_row_sparse_delay(synaptic_word);
    uint32_t combined_synapse_neuron_index = synapse_row_sparse_type_index(
        synaptic_word);
    uint32_t weight = synapse_row_sparse_weight(synaptic_word);

    // Convert into ring buffer offset
    uint32_t ring_buffer_index = synapses_get_ring_buffer_index_combined(
        delay + time, combined_synapse_neuron_index);

    // Add weight to current ring buffer value
    uint32_t accumulation = ring_buffers[ring_buffer_index] + weight;
}

```

Figure 45: From synapses.c (Stokes and Rowley³, 2017)

Indexes in the ring buffer are filled with the extracted components of the synapse row plus a weight value and become what is called a synaptic weight.

Updating input buffers

Before placing the synaptic weight values in input buffers, any existing input buffer elements are first shaped according to the shaping rule specified by the synapse type implementation.

The ring buffer index is obtained for the current time to make sure the right neuron and synapse type is being updated. Then the conversion takes place to put the synaptic weight into the input buffers based on the rule specified by the synapse type.

3.5.7 Synaptic plasticity

Synaptic plasticity is a key process for SpiNNaker to be able to support synaptic models that demonstrate learning as well as neuron models. To adhere to the unpredictable nature of biological STDP, the process is implemented in an event driven manner, where STDP is instigated upon a spike happening only and not bounded by any time driven constraints. In sPyNNaker this is implemented as shown in Figure 46 which gives an algorithm of the STDP process as an overview.

```

1 for each synapse on core with corr. presyn. neuron do
2     find next presynaptic spike (incl. axonal delay);
3     find next postsynaptic spike (incl. dendritic delay);
4     while next spike is before current time do
5         if next spike is presynaptic then
6             update synaptic state (including weight);
7             find next presyn. spike (incl. axonal delay);
8         end
9         if next spike is postsynaptic then
10            update synaptic state (including weight);
11            find next postsyn. spike (incl. dendr. delay);
12        end
13    end
14    update synaptic state to current time;

```

Figure 46: The STDP algorithm implemented in the sPyNNaker API to process pre and post synaptic events in chronological order for each synapse of the neuron model axon (Diehl and Cook, 2014).

The for loop iterates over all the synapses associated with the arriving spike and the weight update occurs at the moment a pre-synaptic event arrives (Line 1). The time of the pre-synaptic event refers to the point in time it was fired by the pre-synaptic neuron. Line 2 calculates the time the pre-synaptic spike was received by the synapse by adding the axonal delay to the spike time. Line 3 calculates when a post-synaptic spike arrives at the synapse by adding the dendritic delay (Diehl and Cook, 2014).

The while loop (lines 4-13) is executed so long as there are spikes to process before the current time. Lines 6, 10 and 14 can vary between different STDP rules and will be areas that will be focused for implementing the Urbanczik-Senn rule. These lines correspond to weight updates depending on the next spike. If the next spike is pre-synaptic a depression occurs and the weight is decreased. If the next spike is post-synaptic potentiation happens, increasing the weight value. The time of the next pre/post synaptic spike is retrieved from the spike time buffer and an axonal/dendritic delay is added (Diehl and Cook, 2014).

As a final step, the synaptic state is updated to the current time to reflect changes from the time the last spike and the state in the current time. The synaptic state consists of a pre-synaptic trace, post-synaptic trace and the plastic synaptic weight. This information is stored in the pre-synaptic spike time buffer (Diehl and Cook, 2014).

Essential files

The following are key API files to enable the execution of STDP on SpiNNaker.

Synapse_dynamics_static_impl.c - In simulations where STDP is not needed, this API file is used to deactivate the plastic synapses.

Synapse_dynamics.h - This file in conjunction with synapse_row.h, provides the necessary infrastructure to process plastic synapses by mapping the synapse data on a synaptic row.

Timing dependence

Whereas neuron models are updated at a given time-step, STDP is activated by the timing of spikes. Therefore, in a network of neurons, not all post-synaptic neurons may be affected by a pre-synaptic spike. Some neurons remain unchanged while others engage in STDP activity. The sPyNNaker API provides some different timing rules in order to determine the amount by which the weight should be changed.

Timing rules	Features
Timing_nearest_pair.h	Only the nearest neighbouring spike is used to calculate the trace. This restricts the range of N spikes to be processed in order of n nearest neighbours to calculate the trace, thus lowering the computational complexity.
Timing_pair.h	Similar to "Timing_nearest_pair" but takes into account every pair of spikes in the input spike buffer to calculate the trace to inform the change in weight which increases the computational complexity.

Timing_pfister_triplet_impl.h	Another form of STDP that uses a third spiking neuron and trace to elicit STDP. This could consist of 1 pre and 2 post neurons or 2 pre and 1 post neuron. This is more computationally expensive as three traces are used instead of just two.
-------------------------------	---

Weight dependence

This component is used in the timing dependence rule to update the weights whenever STDP is activated and describe how the weight update is affected by the current synaptic weight.

Weight dependence rule	What is different
Weight_additive_one_term_impl.h	Weights are added up or subtracted using by a magnitude of a2_plus (potentiation) or a2_minus (depression)
Weight_additive_two_term_impl.h	Uses a third factor 'a3' to add or subtract a larger magnitude of weight change for potentiation or depression
Weight_multiplicative_impl.h	Weights are updated by uses of a scale that is multiplied and added to the weight.

Synapse_dynamics_stdp_mad_impl.c – this file signifies the main STDP loop that processes plastic synapses and applies timing and weight dependence rules. Important methods that achieve this included “_plasticity_update_synapse” which the updates plastic weights based on the correlation between pre and post synaptic spike timings. This result is used in “synapse_dynamics_process_plastic_synapses” convert and add the weight to the ring buffer and write back the updated plastic synaptic word to SDRAM to complete the STDP process.

Existing research into STDP implementation

Since the inception of SpiNNaker, much of the studies into STDP on SpiNNaker have focused on improving implementation of STDP within the constraints imposed by neuromorphic hardware.

Jin et al (2010) implemented an approach where STDP triggered only when the pre-synaptic neuron fired. An associated deferred event driven model was introduced to postpone the STDP process until there was a sufficient history of spike timing records. Diehl and Cook (2014) present a different approach by adopting the same approach by Jin et al (2010) in triggering STDP on pre-synaptic spikes but processes synapse in chronological order, to enable the storing of only one pre and post synaptic trace for each synapse along with any recent spike from the neuron. This simplified the implementation of STDP rules and provided a framework in which to efficiently add new STDP rules.

Galluppi et al (2015) present a very different approach by using extra cores to simulate STDP in a more time driven manner. Dedicated plasticity cores are utilised that operate on a slower timestep to process weight updates while the simulation runs on the cores dedicated to neuron operations. This results in a greater capacity for processing plasticity events in real time. The authors present the

algorithms uses and comment that their approach can be easily extended to include a third factor to modulate plasticity but they do not comment on how this can be done.

Knight and Furber (2016) attempt to improve on the current method of splitting a synapse matrix containing the synapse rows vertically to process plastic events by splitting the synapse matrix horizontally over multiple cores. The improvement comes from being able to keep the row length as long as local memory restrictions allow. When dividing synapses to be processed over multiple cores, the synaptic row length is unaffected. Knight and Furber demonstrate an improvement over the number of neurons per core that are able to be simulated from 60 to 170 using this approach. However, there is little evidence that this has been incorporated into the current sPyNNaker design architecture.

The modifications and enhancements proposed have increased the performance of traditional unsupervised STDP when applied to SpiNNaker. Due to the novelty of the simulator and software these approaches may have been priorities to advance the development of SpiNNaker as a viable simulator for STDP networks. As a result there is little to no research in introducing the use of neuromodulated STDP that use different signals to induce STDP to enable reward based learning or supervised learning paradigms.

Furthermore, the neuron models implemented on SpiNNaker are fairly simplistic in nature. They do not factor in additional state space variables beyond one excitatory and one inhibitory input. Multi-compartmental models do not feature in the current implementation of sPyNNaker which are important to enable the modelling of modulated STDP models. These deficiencies highlighted from a review of the sPyNNaker API serve to explain in more detail the gaps in the state of the art in SpiNNaker that this project intends to address.

4.0 Problem analysis

This chapter conducts an analysis of the problems and details design choices to implement proposed solutions.

4.1 Pyramidal Neuron model

The section explores the problem of implementing a pyramidal neuron as a multi-compartment neuron model in sPyNNaker and analyses the problem in further detail.

4.1.1 Problem description

In the current state of the art of neural modelling on SpiNNaker a neuron model only accepts two types of input one inhibitory and one excitatory input. This is implemented in the sPyNNaker API as a specific synapse type component that includes excitatory and inhibitory. There is no neuron model that can distinguish between two types of excitatory inputs.

Current API implementation of synaptic types to process inputs and update neuron voltage

In the current sPyNNaker API, both excitatory and inhibitory synaptic signals reach the soma using the same process. This process involves passing a combined excitatory or inhibitory input to the neuron using the “synapse_types_get_inhibitory_input” and “synapse_types_get_excitatory_input” methods in the synapse type.

Exponential synapse type implementation

The exponential synapse type possesses one excitatory and one inhibitory synapse per neuron which is represented in the diagram below:

Figure 47: Architecture of the exponential synapse type.

Here there is one channel for each type of input. All excitatory inputs are placed in the excitatory channel and the inhibitory inputs in the inhibitory channel. The red arrows indicate where the “`synapse_types_get_excititory_input`” and “`synapse_types_get_inhibitory_input`” methods are called by neuron.c. The inputs are converted in currents also by neuron.c using the “`input_type_convert_excitatory_input_to_current()`” and “`input_type_convert_inhibitory_input_to_current()`” methods being passed into the neuron state update method.

Dual exponential synapse type implementation

The Dual excitatory (`synapse_types_dual_excitatory_exponential_impl.h`) implementation has two excitatory synapse channels and one inhibitory channel. The dual excitatory synapse implementation is represented below:

Figure 48: The dual exponential synapse type architecture

In this implementation, at each time step the value in the Excitatory1 and Excitatory2 input buffers are added. This is denoted by the red arrows. The combined value is passed to the input type to convert into a current before passing this into the neuron model.

4.1.2 Analysis of the problem

The issue with the current state of the art is the neuron model distinguishes between one type of excitatory input. The reasons why this represents a deficiency are:

The neuron soma only ever receives one excitatory signal

The number of excitatory signals a neuron model receives is known as the state space of the neuron, and refers to the capacity of the neuron to do more complex operations such as learning. The membrane potential entering the soma describes the neuron state in a computation – excitatory inputs increase membrane voltage and inhibitory inputs decrease it. This corresponds to two internal states the neuron can take on.

This is a problem because the state-space of the neuron has been reduced to one, only one excitatory signal is received as a state variable. Inhibitory signals are discounted as they fall under a different learning paradigm that is distinct from excitatory signals (Lamsa, Kullmann and Melanie A. Woodin, 2010). This is an open question in research, and is outside the scope of this project. Due to small state space, neurons in SpiNNaker are not able to support different forms of reinforcement or supervised learning mechanisms that use an internally produced error signal to induce learning. There are no additional membrane signals entering the neuron that it can use to tune separately and therefore increase the state space for processing complex computations. This results in the following implications relevant to the project's problem domain:

A. The sPyNNaker architecture cannot support the modelling of multi-compartment neurons

On a biological level, when a state variable is employed by the neuron it can be seen as a compartment. SpiNNaker neurons only possess one compartment. This makes it unsuitable for modelling multi-compartmental models that employ multiple state variables to simulate more complex behaviour. This places restrictions on the scope of use cases SpiNNaker can be applied to and limits the effectiveness of neuromorphic hardware in neural modelling.

This is important since existing research conducted into L5 pyramidal neurons identify apical and basal dendrites as having separate processing compartments for excitatory inputs. The behaviour of L5 cortex neurons cannot be accurately modelled on neuromorphic hardware as sPyNNaker does not provide the appropriate infrastructure to account for two excitatory compartments.

B. Neuron builds cannot support different learning models that rely on teaching signals

With the limitations of existing neuron models in their state-spaces, there is an issue with the variety of different learning paradigms that the existing models can be applied to. Currently SpiNNaker is limited to simulating forms of Hebbian unsupervised learning such as STDP, relying primarily on the correlation of pre and post spike times and cannot support more directed learning. For instance, it does not distinguish between actions that lead to a positive outcome. Unsupervised Hebbian learning can strengthen connections between neuron resulting in the same action being taken again, but it may not be the best action for a reward.

This is a problem as it reduces the effectiveness of neuromorphic hardware - the benefits of hardware are outweighed by limitations in software. The implications of this are that supervised and reinforcement learning cannot be modelled on SpiNNaker. It is suggested that dopamine is a key excitatory neurotransmitter in changing the excitability of neurons and regulating synaptic plasticity (Frémaux and Gerstner, 2016). It can act as a teaching signal, where decisions leading to a positive result sends a success signal after a delay that strengthens the synaptic connections. The dopamine

signal could be modelled if there was an additional excitatory signal received by the neuron that can be tuned to induce neuromodulated reward-based STDP. The neuron model builds implemented in sPyNNaker do not allow two separate excitatory signals to be received by the soma. These disadvantages will restrict the capabilities and the usefulness of neuromorphic hardware in neural modelling.

4.1.2 Proposed solution

To change the current state of the art the sPyNNaker API will be modified to accept two types of excitatory input. There doesn't exist a multi-compartment excitatory neuron model with which to model apical and basal dendrites.

This is important to note because of the objective to implement a pyramidal neuron model that mimics an entire apical dendritic structure and another compartment to mimic the basal dendritic structure as a first step to be used in more advanced ways for machine learning on the SpiNNaker board.

To achieve this a proposed change to the API is to add functionality to the neuron implementation so it can distinguish between two types of excitatory signals. This is represented below:

Figure 49: Proposed solution for neuron model.

The “Synaptic weight update” area represents the operations involved in processing weight changes. This is not the main focus of this implementation because the problem is how the inputs are received by the neuron model not the synapse, represented as “Neuron Soma”. Thus, it is assumed that the design will use the existing architecture regarding the processing of synaptic weights.

A ring buffer, input buffer and input type will form a ‘channel’. In my design I will require three channels, two excitatory channels and one inhibitory channel. The ring buffers hold the accumulated weights from the weight processing step and the input buffer holds the processed weights in the ring buffer and forms an input. The input value from the buffer is processed by the “Input type” before being passed to the neuron model “Neuron Soma”. This means the neuron receives three inputs in total (1 inhibitory, 2 excitatory) and solves the problem as the neuron soma can then distinguish between an excitatory1 input and excitatory2 input as separate inputs for example.

4.1.3 Analysis of proposed changes

In light of these knowledge of the current architecture, the excitatory and inhibitory channels are implemented already in the existing sPyNNaker architecture. However, what is lacking is a complete infrastructure to support an additional excitatory input to the neuron model. The proposed design solves this problem by introducing a third instance of an input type in order to parse an input from the input buffer to the neuron model. The result is a new state variable is introduced into the neuron soma and increase the state space. The soma is able to tune and maintain a separate signal to execute more complex computations and represents more "storage space". This forms the novel contribution to the current sPyNNaker API that will be made.

4.2 The Urbanczik-Senn Plasticity Rule

This section will analyse the problem of implementing the plasticity rule in more detail.

4.2.1 Problem analysis

Current implementation in sPyNNaker

The Urbanczik-Senn rule is based on ideas present in STDP, but currently, there is no implementation infrastructure to support the above learning rule in the sPyNNaker API. However the existing data flow can be analysed to determine the feasibility of the proposed learning rule and how the changes proposed affect the execution of the STDP.

Data flow of STDP implemented by sPyNNaker

The following diagram of the event driven model is recalled from the Technology review chapter to help visualise how the flow of execution of STDP fits the event driven model during a simulation

In sPyNNaker STDP is activated depending on if `synapse_dynamics_stdp_impl.c` is specified in the Makefile when the C code is compiled. If `synapse_dynamics_static_impl.c` is specified no plastic synapses will be used in simulations. The following data flow is for when STDP is activated for a neuron model build (Rowley, 2017¹):

Step 1 - When a packet event containing a spike is received, it is placed into a spike input buffer which is a DMA buffer struct in the SDRAM of a SpiNNaker node. A DMA transfer is started if not already initiated from the previous spike.

In code this is represented in the "`_multicast_packet_recieved_callback`" method in `spike_processing.c`.

```
// If there was space to add spike to incoming spike queue
if (in_spikes_add_spike(key)) {
```

Figure 50: API code to add spike to spike input buffer in SDRAM (Stokes and Rowley, 2016).

```
if (!dma_busy) {
    log_debug("Sending user event for new spike");
    if (spinl_trigger_user_event(0, 0)) {
        dma_busy = true;
    }
}
```

Figure 51: The line "`dma_busy = true`" triggers a DMA cycle if needed (Stokes and Rowley, 2016).

Step 2 - After this, a DMA processing loop is invoked, where the next spike is read from the spike input buffer and the memory address of the synapses that the incoming spike should be routed to is looked up in a population table. This table is stored on SDRAM to make routing easier by keeping records of each address of the neuron being simulated at the current time step.

The “_setup_synaptic_dma_read” method in spike_processing.c contains the DMA processing loop, where “population_table_get_next_address” method checks for the address :

```
// If there's more rows to process from the previous spike
while (!setup_done && population_table_get_next_address(
    &row_address, &n_bytes_to_transfer)) {

    // This is a direct row to process
    if (n_bytes_to_transfer == 0) {
        _do_direct_row(row_address);
    } else {
        _do_dma_read(row_address, n_bytes_to_transfer);
        setup_done = true;
    }
}
```

Figure 52: The “_setup_synaptic_dma_read” method in spike_processing.c (Stokes and Rowley, 2016).

"population_table_get_next_address" - the address of the synapses for the incoming spike looked up in the population table.

"in_spikes_get_next_spike(&spike)" - reads next spike from the spike input buffer

Step 3- If the address is found in the population table, A DMA event is initiated which transfers the relevant row of the synaptic matrix from SDRAM to the local memory (DTCM) of the node which is invoked by the line “_do_dma_read(row_address, n_bytes_to_transfer);”.

```
// This is a direct row to process
if (n_bytes_to_transfer == 0) {
    _do_direct_row(row_address);
} else {
    _do_dma_read(row_address, n_bytes_to_transfer);
    setup_done = true;
}
}
```

Figure 53: API code to initiate a DMA event (Stokes and Rowley, 2016).

Step 4 - The DMA transfer completes and processes the next initiated transfer if there are additional spikes in the spike input buffer waiting to be processed.

```

// If there's more incoming spikes
cpsr = spin1_int_disable();
while (!setup_done && in_spikes_get_next_spike(&spike)) {
    spin1_mode_restore(cpsr);
    log_debug("Checking for row for spike 0x%.8x\n", spike);

    // Decode spike to get address of destination synaptic row
    if (population_table_get_first_address(
        spike, &row_address, &n_bytes_to_transfer)) {

        // This is a direct row to process
        if (n_bytes_to_transfer == 0) {
            _do_direct_row(row_address);
        } else {
            _do_dma_read(row_address, n_bytes_to_transfer);
            setup_done = true;
        }
    }
    cpsr = spin1_int_disable();
}

if (!setup_done) {
    finished = true;
}
cpsr = spin1_int_disable();

```

Figure 54: Code the check for any more spikes in spike input buffer (Stokes and Rowley, 2016).

Step 5 - The synaptic row transfer is processed and plastic connections (plastic rows) are processed before static connections (fixed rows). For plastic connections:

- a. The last time pre-synaptic neuron is extracted from the plastic synapse row. This happens in the standard STDP loop (synapse_dynamics_stdp_mad_impl.c) in “synapse_dynamics_process_plastic_synapse”.

```

const uint32_t last_pre_time =
    event_history->times[event_history->count_minus_one];

```

Figure 55: API code to get last pre-spike time. (Rowley, Stokes and Davis, 2016)

- b. The post spikes that have been stored since the last pre-spike are retrieved for each plastic connection.

```

post_event_window_t post_window = post_events_get_window(
    post_event_history, begin_time);

```

Figure 56: API code to get post spikes (Rowley, Stokes and Davis, 2016)

- c. The timing rule updates the plastic synaptic weight based on each pair of pre-post spikes, using the **current** spike time (depression).

In the sPyNNaker api C code this is handled by the standard stdp loop (synapse_dynamics_stdp_impl.c or synapse_dynamics_stdp_mad_impl.c) in the plasticity_update_synapse() method.

```

// Apply spike to state
const uint32_t delayed_pre_time = *pre_window.next_time + delay;
current_state = timing_apply_pre_spike(delayed_pre_time,
    *pre_window.next_trace, pre_window.prev_time,
    pre_window.prev_trace, post_window.prev_time,
    post_window.prev_trace, current_state);

```

Figure 57: Timing rule depression (Rowley, Stokes and Davis, 2016)

- d. The timing rule updates the weight based on each pair of pre-post spikes, using the **last pre-spike time** (potentiation). The timing rule uses the weight rule to determine the change in plastic weight.

```
// Apply spike to state
current_state = timing_apply_post_spike(*post_window.next_time,
    *post_window.next_trace, pre_window.prev_time,
    pre_window.prev_trace, post_window.prev_time,
    post_window.prev_trace, current_state);
```

Figure 58: Timing rule potentiation (Rowley, Stokes and Davis, 2016)

Step 6 - After the plastic connections have been processed, the adjusted and static weights are added to the ring buffers of the neurons to perform the delay process (Rowley, 2017¹). This takes place in “synapse_dynamics_process_plastic_synapses()”.

Step 7 - Once the whole row has been processed, the plastic part of the row is written back to SDRAM using another DMA, which happens at the end of “synapse_process_synaptic_row()”.

The following screenshot shows the calling hierarchy for applying a weight potentiation. There will be a similar hierarchy for the weight depression.

Figure 59: Calling hierarchy for weight potentiation

4.2.2 Deficiencies in current implementation

Inflexibility of STDP for different types of neuron models

STDP is optimized and fine tuned for small handful of specific use cases - the point neuron model builds that are there already implemented in sPyNNaker. The following five neuron models have been successfully implemented on SpiNNaker:

- IFCurrExp
- IFCondExp
- IFCurrDualExp
- IZKCurrExp
- IZKCondExp

Almost these models possess one types of synapses – one excitatory and one inhibitory. This has meant that the STDP rule is tailored to work with only two synapses at one time and does not currently accommodate a supervisor current. This is an issue as it becomes inextensible for other learning rules that wish to make use of compartmental models or models with different neuron properties such as more than 2 synapses.

Lack of support for a modulating voltage

This is perhaps the key aspect from the current STDP implementation that is lacking in the sPyNNaker API. This refers to the STDP learning rule being influenced by a third factor – a modulating voltage in addition to pre and post spike timing dependence. This reason why this could be is that the neuron models builds implemented currently lack a clearly defined local dendritic voltage. This is an issue because the hypothesis for the proposed learning rule by Urbanczik and Senn relies on this third quantity to induce plasticity. Without a local dendritic potential, it is currently not possible to support the calculation of a Somato-dendritic prediction error which is considered the key driver for learning in the Urbanczik-Senn rule. Only the correlation between pre and post synaptic spikes are factored in, which is sufficient for standard STDP but not for the purposes of the Urbanczik-Senn rule.

Lack of support for directed weight changes

This deficiency refers to the targeting of weight changes to neuron compartments resulting from the Somato-dendritic prediction error. This is calculated by comparing the potential in the dendritic and somatic compartments. The STDP implementation in sPyNNaker assumes point neuron models and updates the states of excitatory synapse but there is no explicit reference to which excitatory synapse is being updated. This is relevant only in the case of the dual exponential synapse type.

4.2.3 Proposed solution

As a solution, one of my project objective is to identify a design for the Urbanczik-Senn rule to implement in sPyNNaker where the equation is shown in Figure 18:

The idea is to use the multi-compartment model described earlier to modulate the membrane voltage in each compartment. The difference in membrane potential between the two dendritic compartments is taken where the second compartment acts as a teaching signal to the first compartment. If for example, the potential in 1st compartment is higher or lower than the second, then the synaptic weights are adjusted so that the current in both compartments becomes equal.

This drives plasticity by introducing a predictive coding scheme using dendritic voltage to predict spike activity informing STDP. The implications of this is to support more forms of unsupervised learning on neuromorphic hardware. Currently STDP is implemented on the board which can be modified by using different timing and weight dependence rules. With this learning rule a wide variety of biologically motivated learning rules for synapses can be implemented and their behaviour in large scale network simulations can be studied.

This will enable further investigation into how low-level synaptic plasticity can induce learning behaviour in massively parallel computation systems. This can be utilised to inform a greater understanding on the intricacies of human brain operation and to contribute towards the construction of next-generation computing hardware including SpiNNaker, that is an advancement from the conventional Von-Neuman architecture as this is reaching its physical limits regarding energy consumption and further miniaturisation. Cognitive software combined with appropriately designed brain inspired hardware could enable more advanced AI systems as learning is more in tune to how a human acquires knowledge. It is for this reason that the proposed solution is a worthy line of enquiry to investigate to improve the current SpiNNaker platform.

5.0 Design choices

This section will discuss the design choices that have been taken to implement the proposed solutions.

5.1 Technology choices

Operating system - Windows will be used to implement and test neural modelling code as the author feels most accustomed to it and is supported by the SpiNNaker build tools. GNU Linux is also supported and can be more powerfully used in principle if the correct commands are known. The author gained experience in using the Linux shell in their Industrial Placement to perform system operations and is comfortable with using the tools.

Later in the project the Windows programming environment suffered a corruption that could not be address easily or quickly. GNU Linux was used to install a new instance of the SpiNNaker build tools to continue implementation.

Programming languages - Due to programming constraints imposed by the sPyNNaker framework C and Python will be used. C will be used to implement the neuron functionality and Python will be used to create a PyNN description of the model for use in experiments.

Programming environment - Eclipse has been tested for use by the SpiNNaker development team and is recommended. Useful plugins such as CDT can support C development along with PyDev that supports Python making Eclipse a versatile editor.

Software packages

The following python packages will be vital in implementing the neuron model and learning as well as any other PyNN experiments.

NumPy – This is a core extension to the Python programming language, providing structures functions to dynamically manipulate numbers (Numpy.org, n.d.). This will be used to store and access arrays of spikes.

Scipy – another commonly used package that provides mathematical and scientific tools to manipulate data (Scipy.org, n.d.). This will used in conjunction with NumPy to provide all necessary tools to manipulate numeric data.

Matplotlib – a comprehensive 2D plotting package that will be used to visualise results from experiments (Matplotlib.org, n.d.).

PyNN – the python interface (Davison, 2008) giving access to important neural modelling code that sPyNNaker interfaces with to provide PyNN functionality to SpiNNaker.

SpiNNaker development build tools

The following will detail the SpiNNaker specific build tools to be used.

Spinnaker_tools	Provides utilities to support the general running of the system board such as bootstrapping code (SC&MP), SARK, Spin1 API and ybug.
-----------------	---

Spin_common	A support library for C programming on SpiNNaker by providing standard fixed point arithmetic operations, a circular buffer support library and a random number generator.
SpiNNUtils	A support python module that provides basic utility functions and classes to support the loading of resources onto the SpiNNaker system.
SpiNNMachine	This package is used to implement a python representation of a SpiNNaker machine.
SpiNNStorageHandlers	Provides classes to handle data storage.
PACMAN	Provides functionality to map PyNN networks on SpiNNaker.
SpiNNMan	Interfaces with the SpiNNaker board.
DataSpecification	A module that creates a memory image to aid performance of slow connection from the host to the board.
SpiNNFrontEndCommon	Translates application level programs into executables for the Spinnaker machine.
sPyNNaker	The SpiNNaker optimised version of PyNN which implements a subset of PyNN 0.75.
sPyNNakerNewModelTemplate	A recommended template structure to implement neuron models.

Hardware choices

The SpiNNaker system currently comes in the form of SpiNN-3 and SpiNN-5 board shown below:

Figure 60: A 4 node general purpose SpiNN-3 board (Apt.cs.manchester.ac.uk, n.d.3).

Figure 61: A 48-node SpiNN-5 board (Stromatias et al., 2015)

A 48 node board is mainly stacked with other SpiNN-5 boards in a rack as part of the main SpiNNaker machine located in Manchester university. While it is possible to obtain this board specification to model larger scale spiking neural networks, The University of Surrey Computing Department has been loaned a SpiNN-3 board. Consequently, this will be the board that will be used for this project. This will be sufficient computing power for the purposes of this project since the primary focus is to demonstrate neuron and learning capabilities, which can be done with a smaller scale neural network.

5.2 Software development lifecycle (SDLC)

An SDLC is a structured sequence of planned activities to develop or alter software. There are a range of different standard approaches that are used to develop software that are suitable for different kinds of projects. This section will be a discussion of a selection of standard SDLC's used in industry to determine their viability for this project.

5.2.1 SDLC phases

There are six stages integral to all SDLC's.

Stage 1: Requirements gathering and analysis – In this stage, information gathering techniques are used to establish the problem and form the requirements for the system such as the people who will be using the system and how they want to use it. This information is gathered through meetings with key stakeholders involving managers and users and forms requirements. An analysis of the requirements is conducted to determine their validity and a software requirement specification (SRS) document is created to guide the design phase.

Stage 2: Design – The SRS is used as a frame of reference to design the architecture of the system to propose as a solution to the problem and to meet the requirements.

Stage 3: Implementation – The design architecture is implemented in code by developers and is typically the longest phase of the SDLC.

Stage 4: Testing – The code developed from the implementation stage is tested against the requirements to verify if they are met or not. This is achieved through functional and non-functional testing. Various types of functional tests can be used to achieve this such as unit testing, integration testing and acceptance testing.

Stage 5: Deployment – If testing is successful the software product is delivered to the client for use. Beta testing might be used as a deployment method where an 'alpha' product is shipped to a select group of clients to report any bugs in the code. After bug fixes the software can undergo a final mass deployment

Stage 6: Maintenance – Once the product has been deployed for client use, issues may arise in the use of the software. Maintenance is concerned with addressing these issues.

5.2.2 Waterfall model

The waterfall model is shown in figure and is one of the earliest approaches used for software development. There are six stages and each stage only begins if the previous stage has been completed in a linear structure analogous to a waterfall. Typically, each stage informs the next stage.

Figure 62: The Waterfall model (tutorialspoint, 2017¹)

Projects that are most suited to this type of SDLC are projects whose requirements are well documented, clear and fixed. Also the technology is stable and not likely to change along with a short project duration are reasons to adopt this approach. The benefits of using the waterfall method are that it is easy and simple to understand and follow. Stages are clearly defined, well documented and completed one at a time and milestones can be easily understood. However the major disadvantages of the waterfall model are that no working software is created until late in the development cycle. If problems are encountered at this stage, it is difficult to correct as the cumulative effects of the stages mean that other stages of the project must be changed which may be cumbersome. This could be problematic in long projects where requirements could change at later stages due to implementation challenges or time constraints.

5.2.3 Agile model

The Agile model focuses on an incremental process to develop software with emphasis on adaptability to respond to changing client requirements quickly. At the end of each iteration a working software product is built to be evaluated by the client and identify changes to be made in the next iteration.

Figure 63: The Agile model (tutorialspoint, 2017²)

This approach is most suited to projects that enable close collaboration with clients who are willing to engage with the iterative nature of the agile model. Advantages of adopting this approach over waterfall include flexibility of change early on in the development process and is good for environments that are prone to change. However the success of the methodology rests more on clear communication with the client. If they are not clear on the requirements, then the team could be misguided. There is also a high dependency on the individual since there is minimal documentation of each stage.

5.2.4 Iterative model

The iterative model is characterised by a simple implementation of a small set of requirements and builds on this by iteratively adding features over time until the full system is implemented. Characteristics of projects that would likely suit this approach would be those with a time constraint to release to the market. Another characteristic is if there is a new technology that needs to be learnt during development or if expertise is needed for certain feature but are used on a contractual basis for certain iterations.

Figure 64: The Iterative model (tutorialspoint, 2017³)

An advantage of this model includes early results from developing functionality early in the life cycle. Every increment delivers an operational product. Any requirements that need to be changed can be done in a less costly way through increments. However some disadvantages are that more resources may be needed to facilitate this model. With each iteration the whole SDLC has to be followed which draw out the length of time this model takes, making it heavy and unsuitable for short projects.

5.2.5 Big bang model

A key aspect of this model is the emphasis of the implementation phase with minimal to no prior planning or documentation. Requirements are established and implemented as and when they come. It is appropriate for small projects where the problem is clearly defined with minimal risks. Advantages of this model are that it is very simple, with little planning required. It is straightforward to organise and direct with few resources required. However it could be considered the most riskiest of the discussed models since any misunderstood requirements may lead to large scale changes or a complete abandonment of the project due to lack of planning and documentation (tutorialspoint, 2017¹).

5.2.6 Design choice

When considering a model to follow the nature of the project is important to factor into account. The project is intended to be a research orientated project that aims to undertake novel scientific

research to discover new ways of emulating human behaviour on neuromorphic hardware. This will involve taking the existing sPyNNaker API and extending it to implement new functionality. Any proposed API enhancements are not considered to be a substantial system and is not user based.

Therefore, it has been considered that a full SDLC is not required to be extensively followed but rather aspects of a model can be adopted. For example, to achieve the objectives of the project, it is very likely that an extensive documentation of the existing design architecture will need to be conducted, down to the execution flow at the code level on how important processes such as STDP is implemented. The Waterfall model is appropriate for this approach as the existing architecture must be studied extensively to identify the enhancements to be made and to acquire confidence that they will work. Only then can the implementation and testing stages commence. Functional requirements are very clear from the beginning as they have been established from biological principles and can be taken forward to design.

However due to the novelty of this project it is not known if the changes will be successful until the implementation stage and testing stage and will be a process of discovery. The existing design is subject to revisions to fit into the current architecture of sPyNNaker in response to new knowledge acquired about system constraints. Therefore an agile approach will be suitable to employ a more iterative approach but will omit requirements analysis since they are established and inflexible to change.

5.3 Project stages

There is a dependency apparent in the project, where the pyramidal neuron model is required to be implemented first before the learning rule can be implemented since it will use the neuron dynamics to function.

Given this, the project will be split into the following milestones:

Design for neuron model:

- Identify suitable API enhancements to inform the design of the pyramidal neuron

Implementation and verification for neuron model:

- Implement the proposed pyramidal neuron model design
- Verify correct functionality of neuron model through experimentation

Design for learning rule:

- Identify a suitable algorithmic implementation for the Urbanczik-Senn plasticity rule compatible with SpiNNaker.

Implementation and testing:

- Implement Urbanczik-Senn plasticity rule
- Verify correct functionality of learning rule through experiments

5.4 Design architecture - Pyramidal neuron model

Given the analysis of the problem and the proposed solution, the following is a discussion of key design issues and design choices that will be made to implement the solution.

The following are the key stages of implementation:

1. Create initial test case
2. Identify key API files to change
3. Implement proposed changes
4. Establish choice of experiments to test the multicompartment neuron

This section will focus on the first two stages related to design of the system.

5.4.1 Requirements

Taking the complete neuron model build to be the system that should be built, establishing initial requirements is important to ensure that the correct system is built and to guide implementation.

The requirements for the neuron model are:

Functional Requirements:

F.1 - The system must be able to distinguish between two excitatory inputs at each time step

F.2 - The system must be able to receive one inhibitory input at each time step

F.3 - The system must calculate its membrane voltage at each time step to determine if it should spike

F.4 - The system must reset the membrane voltage and refractory timer if it spikes

F.5 - The system must allow the following neuron parameters to be set:

- Membrane voltage
- Membrane resting voltage
- Membrane resistance
- Offset current
- Refractory period timer
- Post spike reset membrane voltage
- Refractory time of neuron

F.6 The system should receive an external bias current

Non-functional requirements:

NF1 - The system must be available to use PyNN scripts for experiments

NF2 - The system will use two excitatory synapses and one inhibitory synapse

NF3 - The system must use the SpiNNaker system board as a simulator

NF4 - The system must be compiled into an executable in accordance to the SpiNNaker system board

Justification of requirements

These requirements are suitable as they have been informed by a review of the underlying biological principles and through one-on-one meetings with the supervisor. Functional requirement F1 is considered the most important feature that should be in the neuron model, since this dynamic will be utilised by the Urbanczik-Senn rule to instigate STDP.

5.4.2 Design constraints

5.4.2.1 SpiNNaker constraints

It is important to note the hardware level constraints when designing the neuron model build and one of the key constraint is the fact that SpiNNaker provides no hardware to support multi-compartmental models. Instead it is optimised for point-neuron models where neuron inputs ignore dendritic components and apply current inputs straight to the neuron soma. This is an issue as the proposed novel implementation will require emulation of dendritic behaviour in compartments.

5.4.2.2 Software Constraints

The current software architecture of the sPyNNaker API supports only the processing of a maximum of two inputs to a neuron in neuron.c. My design must take into account this limitation or implement additional code to support the main implemented functions.

5.4.3 Initial test case

An initial test case will be created before implementing API changes to measure the behaviour of the multi-compartment pyramidal neuron and will inform preliminary experiments. The test case is a neuron model build that uses existing components of the sPyNNaker API.

This will provide a neuron model to be modified and allow me to compare existing results with test results to judge the quality of the changes.

The components that will be used for the neuron model are:

5.4.3.1 Neuron model

The neuron model component is vital to the collection of components that make a neuron model build. The Leaky-Integrate-and-Fire (Neuron_model_lif_impl.h/c) will be used for the initial test case as it is a simpler neuron model. This is because it is intended to be a high-level abstraction and omits biological parameters for ease of analysis and simulation.

This is evidenced in the ordinary differential equation (ODE) describing the change in membrane voltage in response to input currents.

The LIF ODE is presented below:

```
static inline void _lif_neuron_closed_form(  
    neuron_pointer_t neuron, REAL V_prev, input_t input_this_timestep) {  
  
    REAL alpha = input_this_timestep * neuron->R_membrane + neuron->V_rest;  
  
    // update membrane voltage  
    neuron->V_membrane = alpha - (neuron->exp_TC * (alpha - V_prev));  
}
```

Figure 65: The LIF neuron ordinary differential equation (ODE) (Rowley, 2015³).

Here, an alpha is computed by adding the membrane resistance with the resting voltage and multiplying this with the total input current applied to the neuron model. This method is called in the neuron_model_state_update_method(), where the total input is calculated:

```

// Get the input in nA
input_t input_this_timestep =
    exc_input - inh_input + external_bias + neuron->I_offset;

```

Figure 66: calculation of total input (Rowley, 2015³).

The membrane voltage is then updated in the ODE, where the previous membrane voltage from the last time step (V_{prev}) is subtracted from the alpha value. The result is multiplied by a computation parameter 'exp_TC' which is a time-constant multiplier for a closed form solution. This result is subtracted from the alpha value to obtain the new membrane voltage for the current timestep.

5.4.3.2 Input type

For this project, I will be using current based input type (input_type_current.h).

5.4.3.3 Threshold type

I will be using a static threshold (threshold_type_static.h) since it is the only implementation of a threshold in SpiNNaker. This takes the form of a hardcoded value to which the current membrane voltage is compared to.

```

typedef struct threshold_type_t {
    // The value of the static threshold
    REAL threshold_value;
} threshold_type_t;

```

Figure 67: API code for threshold struct (Rowley⁴, 2015).

5.4.3.4 Synapse type

Since a compartment is a segment of the dendritic branch which processes inputs, a design decision I have made is to treat the ring and input buffers of a synapse along with the input type as one "compartment" so as to emulate dendritic behaviour to configure input weights and shape ring buffer weight inputs to place into the input buffers, according to the shaping rules specific to the synapse type. With this idea in mind, we can evaluate the synapse types offered by the sPyNNaker API.

The exponential synapse type has only 2 channels, one for inhibitory and one for excitatory inputs. In order to implement the multi-compartment model, I will need to duplicate the ring and input buffers as well as an input type to be able to convert the input into a current to pass to the neuron. However, the dual-excitatory synapse implementation already has two excitatory channels, each one possessing its own ring and input buffers and input type. The necessary infrastructure is in place, including input buffer regions and methods to process and shape ring buffer inputs for all regions.

```

typedef enum input_buffer_regions {
    EXCITATORY_ONE, EXCITATORY_TWO, INHIBITORY,
} input_buffer_regions;

```

Figure 68: Input buffer regions for both excitatory and inhibitory synapse ids (Stokes and Rowley, 2017¹)

Therefore, the dual excitatory synapse type implementation will be used (synapse_types_dual_excitatory_impl.h) as it was deemed unnecessary to propose a new method of handling inputs as the existing architecture can be adopted on which to apply the enhancements.

5.4.3.5 Synapse dynamics

The 'static' implementation of plasticity is an interface that does not activate plastic synapses (synapses that dynamically change their weights when post-synaptic spikes occur).

If I were to use plastic synapses, timing and weight rules will need to be implemented for the neuron build to work. Therefore a static implementation of synapse dynamics (synapse_dynamics_static_impl.c) will be used in the first iteration since it is quick to implement and operation of plastic synapses are not needed to solve the problem of distinguishing two types of excitatory inputs. For the first design, I want to focus on implementing just the neuron model as a first step to be iterated upon in later designs.

5.4.3.6 Neuron components not considered

The additional input type was deemed to not be suitable for the test case neuron build. This is primarily due to the component being supported only by the sPyNNakerExtraModels API and is outside the scope of sPyNNaker API. This software is not supported by the PyNN language and therefore is supported only in SpiNNaker using the SpiNNaker Graph Front End. The neuron builds shown in are constructed using the same type of components but from implementations optimised exclusively for the SpiNNaker technology. This poses the problem where standard neuron models cannot be implemented easily which is a key issue as it would make it unnecessarily difficult to implement a standard neuron model to test.

5.4.4 API enhancements

The second step after establishing the initial test case is to identify the API files I will need to modify to support the modelling of the multi-compartmental pyramidal neuron model. The following files will be used in the neuron model makefile and will implement the functionality to distinguish between two excitatory inputs.

5.4.4.1 Synapse_types_dual_excitatory_impl.h

This file provides functionality to process the excitatory inputs in the input buffer. Enhancements proposed include an accessor methods named synapse_types_get_excitatory_input() and synapse_types_get_excitatory_input2() that returns separately the excitatory input buffer element.

5.4.4.2 Neuron_model_lif_impl.c

This file is critical to the whole neuron model build as it describes how the neuron responds to inputs. The neuron_model_state_update() will be modified to include and "exc_input2" parameter as input.

Supporting API structure

The following is a discussion of key API files that will provide the infrastructure to enable the neuron model to operate within the wider sPyNNaker API. This is a crucial step to making the model compatible with the rest of the API to be able to conduct experiments with it.

Neuron.c

This file has been identified for modification as it is the main interface of a neuron on the SpiNNaker system responsible for initialising the model and describes how to update the membrane voltage and cause spikes to be produced.

The key method to focus on is `neuron_do_timestep_update()` as it calls methods from the synapse type implementation to shape the synaptic inputs and the neuron model type to update the membrane voltage. Specifically, I will need to shape the input value in a second excitatory input buffer of the synapse and enable this value to be converted to a current to be received by the neuron model.

This is intended to be achieved by using the existing “`input_type_get_input_value()`” method to retrieve the input current from the EXCITATORY_TWO synapse id and “`input_type_convert_excitatory_input_to_current()`” to convert it into an input to be received by the `neuron_model_state_update` function.

Currently, the method only does this for one excitatory input, since only one excitatory value is ever passed to the neuron model. This is the same with the inhibitory input.

Synapse_types.h

The file requires modification because it is the main header file for the dual excitatory synapse implementation. This means that the method signatures must be defined in this file to be used in synapse type implementations.

A design choice is to add another method signature to obtain the input value from the 2nd excitatory channel.

Neuron_model.h

I have identified this file to modify as it the header file from which all neuron models should extend from this file. The method signature to be modified is the `neuron_model_state_update` method, to accept an additional excitatory input.

```
state_t neuron_model_state_update(
    input_t exc_input, input_t inh_input, input_t external_bias,
    neuron_pointer_t neuron);
```

Figure 69: Neuron_model_state_update method signature from neuron_model.h Rowley, A. (2015²).

Figure 70: A modified diagram of the C architecture of the sPyNNaker API adapted from (Stokes, 2015). Modified parts of the diagram are highlighted in yellow where the “Input types” and “Threshold types” already exist in the API.

5.4.5 Python model build

A corresponding Python model build will be required to enable the model to be used in experiments. The following class diagram has been created to visualise the classes needed. The build file `my_model_curr_dual_exp` will be created by the author that will adapt example build files with different neuron properties to produce new results. Existing neuron model components will be used since python files do not hold functionality but merely describe the network so no changes are required. The following components will be used from the existing API architecture to construct the build and are not created by the author:

- SynpaseTypeDualExponential
- `_DUAL_EXP_TYPES`
- ThresholdTypeStatic
- `_STATIC_TYPES`
- InputTypeCurrent
- NeuronModelLeakyIntegrateAndFire
- `_LIF_TYPES`

Figure 71: Class diagram for python model build “my_model_curr_exp”.

5.4.6 Challenging aspects of proposed design

The following is a discussion of aspects of the design that may be challenging to implement.

Test case

Creating the test neuron build from existing components could be challenging as it is made up from a collection of neuron model components. The issue here is conforming to the requirements of the sPyNNaker API where the parameters specified in C code must match exactly to the python code. This is most apparent when specifying parameters in the header file of a neuron model component. This contains the struct data structure that defines the neuron parameters. In the corresponding python code for the neuron model.

```

typedef struct neuron_t {
    // Variable-state parameters e.g. membrane voltage
    REAL V;
    // offset current [nA]
    REAL I_offset;

    REAL my_parameter;

    REAL decay;

    REAL rest_Voltage;
} neuron_t;
typedef struct global_neuron_params_t {
    def get_neural_parameters(self):
        return [
            # REAL V;
            NeuronParameter(self._v_init, DataType.S1615),
            # REAL I_offset;
            NeuronParameter(self._i_offset, DataType.S1615),
            # REAL my_parameter;
            NeuronParameter(self._my_neuron_parameter, DataType.S1615),
            #REAL decay from my neuron_model_impl.h
            NeuronParameter(self.decay, DataType.S1615),
            # REAL rest_Voltage my_neuron_model_impl.h
            NeuronParameter(self.rest_Voltage, DataType.S1615)
        ]

```

Figure 72: (Left): C code describing neuron parameters (Rowley¹, 2016). Right: corresponding python code that declares all the C parameters including the correct order (Rowley², 2016).

The reason for this is the tight coupling between C and python code where C defines the executable and Python describes the ‘infrastructure’ to enable the neuron build to be simulated. For a neuron model component, this includes specifying and initialising values for the neuron parameters and providing accessor methods. These two must agree so that the correct parameters are held in the correct locations in SDRAM memory when passed to the C code during simulations.

Supporting API files

The non-modularity of the system makes it appear complex, where the main issue is that it is known that the API can support fundamental changes in its core architecture. There may be other API files unaccounted for that have not been uncovered during the API overview, problem analysis and design whose functionality is dependent on the correct configuration of the neuron time step update. This could be due to the novelty of the approach as there are no existing implementations of multi-compartmental neurons currently in sPyNNaker. This make for an exciting challenge but risky as there are many unknowns. To mitigate this issue, an extensive overview of the API has been conducted, information has been gathered from SMEs and the implementation will commence early on in the project timeline to respond to any issues that may arise.

5.4.7 Summary of design choices

The following is a summary of the design choices that have been made and to clarify the exact enhancements to the API that will be made.

Neuron model components for test case:

- Neuron model component: Leaky integrate-and-fire
- Synapse type component: synapse_types_dual_excitatory_exponential.h
- Threshold component: threshold_type_static.h
- Synapse dynamics component: synapse_dynamics_static_impl.c
- Input type component: input_type_current.h

Proposed enhancements:

- Neuron model component receives an additional excitatory input
- Neuron model uses the additional excitatory input to calculate membrane voltage

- The synapse type will provide functionality to access both input currents separately from each excitatory input buffer

Supporting API structure:

- An excitatory channel will be implemented by implementing additional input type processing to shape and pass the additional input to the neuron
- Modifying neuron model and synapse header files to support neuron model build changes

5.5 Design Choices of plasticity rule

This section will detail the design choices that have been considered when proposing a design for the Urbanczik-Senn plasticity rule.

5.5.1 Design constraints on SpiNNaker

There are design limitations imposed in SpiNNaker that are important to note before providing the design of the updated learning rule in software.

Memory limitations

The SpiNNaker hardware lacks a globally shared memory resource compared to a conventional computer. By this we refer to a dedicated hardware I/O that is used to load and store program code or simulation data. Instead this data is loaded onto local memory into SDRAM.

For the purposes of designing the Urbanczik-Senn learning rule careful considerations on how any new quantities are introduced into the simulation need to be taken so they can be accessed by different operations in SpiNNaker such as STDP at all times. For example, a modulation voltage is required by the Urbanczik-Senn and this will need to be accessible whenever the synaptic weights should be updated. This could equate to the quantity being calculated whenever it is needed to circumvent the limitation to setting it as a global variable.

Event driven model

While neuron models are simulated in a standard time driven way plasticity is simulated in an event driven manner – synapses are updated only when transferring spikes. To be able to simulate large numbers of synapses to effectively model STDP, synaptic weights are stored in the SDRAM off chip. The result of this design decision is that now, there is not enough memory bandwidth of the SDRAM to accommodate the updating of every synapse parameter per time step. This means an event driven approach has been employed whereby DMA transfers are initiated to retrieve the correct weights for the neuron ID.

The implications of this for the proposed learning rule is that it must conform to this approach when updating synaptic weights. This means that it should handle weights stored in SDRAM and initiate DMA transfers to fetch the synaptic row associated with the firing neuron.

5.5.2 Constraints on sPyNNaker

Calling priority

Within the sPyNNaker implementation of STDP timing rules to signify weight updates are called in the process that has the highest priority. When information about pre-spiking activity arrives to the spike buffer and is read by a DMA, the process is deemed high priority. Timing and weight

dependence rules are called which interrupt whatever is happening at that moment in time. For the proposed learning rule, this may be important when deciding the functions in which to place the calculation of any quantities needed by the timing rule and the sequence of calculating them.

5.5.3 Requirements

With the previously discussed issues in mind the initial requirements for the learning rule are as follows:

Functional requirements:

- F1. The learning rule will initiate Long term potentiation if pre-synaptic spike arrive **before** post-synaptic spikes
- F2. The learning rule will initiate long term depression if pre-synaptic spike arrive **after** post-synaptic spikes
- F3. The learning rule will describe weight changes by using a weight dependence rule
- F4. The learning rule must obtain a current difference between dendritic and somatic compartments
- F5. The learning rule must use the obtained current difference to determine synaptic weight changes

Non-functional requirements:

- NF1. The learning rule must be available to use in PyNN scripts for experiments
- NF2. The learning rule must use the SpiNNaker system board as a simulator

5.5.4 Discussion of modifying API Files

The API files that are to be modified are outlined to implement the required components for the Urbanczik-Senn learning rule. As a pre-requisite, the neuron model created in the first milestone will be used facilitate the rule functionalities.

A decision that has been taken to conform to the event driven nature of synaptic weight update is to base the planned modifications on the current STDP rule. This is appropriate as the research hypothesis presented by Urbanczik and Senn is an extension of standard STDP but introduces a third quantity to induce plasticity. Therefore, the rule utilises the same operations as the standard sPyNNaker implementation regarding the correlation of pre and post synaptic spike times through timing and weight dependence rules.

5.5.4.1 Introducing a modulating voltage

As discussed previously, this is the key differentiating factor that separates standard STDP and the Urbanczik-Senn plasticity rule. This constitutes a current difference between the dendritic and the somatic compartments. Since only point neurons are supported on SpiNNaker assumptions will need to be made on what parts of the neuron model will constitute the dendritic and somatic compartments since sPyNNaker lacks explicitly named compartment instances.

Therefore it is proposed that the excitatory channels will constitute dendritic compartments and the neuron model will form the somatic compartment. The reason for this is to stay accurate with research conducted by Urbanczik-Senn. Where each excitatory dendritic compartment possesses a membrane potential, The soma copies the potential from compartment one, and compares it to

compartment two. If there is a difference between then then the synaptic weights are adjusted in compartment one proportional to $\Delta U = U_2 - U_1$. Thus, compartment two acts as a teaching signal to direct weight potential or depression.

Informed by the constraints imposed by sPyNNaker, the following are proposed locations in which to place the calculation of the current difference to ensure it can be accessed by the timing rule.

Inside the neuron model component

Reprising the LIF implementation for the pyramidal neuron model, this will involve placing the calculation inside this file as a callable method. An additional neuron variable will be added in the neuron struct present in the header file of the LIF component. The method will be called in the neuron state update method and use the excitatory inputs already received by the method. It can be argued that this is the easiest way to calculate the potential difference as the input currents are already passed in to the method so it will be trivial to take the inputs and perform the calculation. When a pre-synaptic spike is received and STDP activated the calculation is already performed when the pre-synaptic neuron fired. The timing rule only needs to retrieve this value from the neuron model struct. This may involve inputting the neuron ID so that the timing rule knows which neuron's current difference should be accessed.

Inside the timing rule

This implementation refers to accessing the input buffers of the excitatory synapses from the timing rule and retrieving the input currents. The calculation will be performed in the timing rule (timing_rule_pair.h) itself. This poses more of a challenge since the synapses as well as the neuron in question will need to be accounted for in the timing rule. This will equate to including the synapse ID and the neuron ID as inputs in a new function to access the values in the input buffers of each excitatory synapse as shown by the function prototype:

```
“static input_t synapse_types_get_input(input_t *input_buffers, index_t neuron_index, index_t synapse_type_index)”
```

The neuron_index refers to the neuron ID and the synapse_type_index is the synapse ID. This refers to the synapse ID being either EXCITATORY_ONE, EXCITATORY_TWO or INHIBITORY.

5.5.4.2 Design choice and justification

When comparing the two approaches neither one suggests that it will be difficult to implement. Therefore, the final decision would be determined by which method would be least computationally expensive and could be more straight forward the implement. The timing rule is called many more times compared to the neuron state update method and each time it is called the current difference will be calculated. This could produce further issues for simulations running for longer periods of time due to local memory constraints on the SpiNNaker chip. Based on the above reasons, the current difference calculation will be implemented in the neuron model component.

5.5.4.3 Initiating and directing weight changes

This modification refers to how the timing rule would direct the weight changes once the current difference has been calculated and retrieved. Firstly, the current difference must be used to determine whether weights should be potentiated or depressed. This will involve the comparisons to be made

```
if(current_difference > 0) { //ex1_current is greater than
ex2_current
// depress EXCITATORY_ONE synapse
}
if(current_difference < 0) { //ex1_current is less than
ex2_current
// add potentiation to EXCITATORY_ONE synapse
} else {
```

Figure 73: Timing Rule changes incorporating a current difference.

The timing rule would be the most suitable the location for the comparisons since it is the primary interface governing how weights should updated using the correlation of pre and post spike timings. For instance, it calls the weight update methods to apply potentiation or depression. Hence an additional comparison can be made to initiate a potentiating of depression of plastic weights.

Other design choices that were not considered included in the main STDP loop (Synapse_dynamics_stdp.impl.c) and more specifically the “_plasticity_update_synapses()”. In the current API implementation, the timing rules are called in a while loop in the “current state variable”:

```
// If next pre-synaptic event occurs before the next post-synaptic event
if (pre_valid
    && (!post_valid
        || (*pre_window.next_time + delay)
           <= *post_window.next_time)) {
    log_debug("\t\tApplying pre-synaptic event at time:%u",
              *pre_window.next_time + delay);

    // Apply spike to state
    const uint32 t delayed_pre_time = *pre_window.next_time + delay;
    current_state = timing_apply_pre_spike(delayed_pre_time,
      *pre_window.next_trace, pre_window.prev_time,
      pre_window.prev_trace, post_window.prev_time,
      post_window.prev_trace, current_state);

    // Go onto next event
    pre_window = pre_events_next(pre_window, delayed_pre_time);
}
```

Figure 74: an example of a pre-spike timing rule being called when a pre-synaptic neuron fires before a post synaptic neuron (Rowley, Stokes, and Davis, 2016).

Later in design it was realised that if the current difference comparison was introduced here, it would undermine the correlation between pre-post synaptic spike times by being dependent on another quantity unrelated to these timings. The STDP mechanism as a whole would be undermined

as this is not the objective to modify the relationship dynamics of spike timings but to modify how weights should be changed in light of the timings. The timing correlation between pre and post spikes are a precursor to weight updates and these should not be changed for the purposes of the Urbanczik-Senn rule.

Targeting weight changes to specific synapse compartments will be the final stage of the STDP mechanism. In PyNN this can be achieved by using the 'target' attribute when defining a projection between neuron populations. The projection will be made a plastic connection and this will fulfil the objective of directing weight changes. The simulation experiment will be responsible for this and would be the most straightforward method since it is built in to PyNN.

Other design choices that were considered but not taken forward were to explicitly state the excitatory synapse type to update in the timing rule updates using the synapse ID. This was deemed unnecessarily complex due to a couple of reasons. Firstly, this would make the timing rule rigid to a particular synapse type ID. Since STDP also happens on inhibitory synapses additional timing rules would be required to account for LTP and LTD on these synapse IDs. This would require an additional input to the weight update shown by the function prototype below, where **EXCITATORY_ONE** refers to the synapse ID:

```
"weight_one_term_apply_depression(previous_state, decayed_o1, EXCITATORY_ONE);"
```

The above provides second reason where by the weight dependence rule would require fundamental changes that may have a knock-on effect on other API components such as other STDP rules. Even if the parameters were kept generic such as "synapse_type_id", additional code would be needed to input the correct synapse type. Due to the complexity of the sPyNNaker design architecture, a design objective is to minimise the amount fundamental architectural changes required to implement the learning rule, and using established functions in Python represent a more efficient way to achieve this goal.

5.5.5 Proposed Algorithm

Given the above design choices, the extended algorithm for the Urbanczik-Senn is presented. The red text highlights the major extensions from standard STDP implemented in the existing sPyNNaker architecture.

Step 0: Current difference is calculated in the neuron model and stored as a variable in the neuron struct

Step 1: The neuron spikes and a spike packet event is received and placed in to a spike input buffer

Step 2: A DMA processing loop reads the next spike and the destination memory address of the synapse is looked up in the population table.

Step 3: A DMA transfer initiates and completes a transfer of the relevant synaptic row to local memory of the node.

Step 4: DMA transfers are completed for the remaining spikes waiting to be processed.

Step 5: Plastic connections are processed:

Step 5a: The last spiking time of the pre-synaptic neuron is extracted from the row.

Step 5b: the post spikes that have occurred since the last pre-spike occurred are obtained.

Step 5c: The current difference is retrieved from the neuron struct of the pre-synaptic neuron.

Step 5d: The timing rule updates the plastic synaptic weight based on each pair of pre-post synaptic spikes using the **current** spike time. If the current difference is greater than zero, weights will be depressed.

Step 5e: The timing rule updates the plastic synaptic weight based on each pair of pre-post synaptic spikes using the **last pre-spike** time. If the current difference is Less than zero, weights will be potentiated.

Step 6: The adjusted weights and static weights are added to the ring buffers to perform the delay process and convert to input currents to inform the next spike.

Step 7: Spike processing completes as normal – the plastic synaptic row is written back to SDRAM through a DMA.

5.5.6 Justification of solution

A novel solution has been designed to act as a first step to implementation not only on the SpiNNaker platform, but neuromorphic hardware. This design can solve the problem of implementing the Urbanczik-Senn rule as it satisfies the requirement for a modulating voltage that the rule relies on. If the current difference is greater than zero, it means that the input current in the excitatory one compartment is higher than excitatory two. Conversely, A current difference less than zero mean the current in the first excitatory compartment is lower than excitatory compartment two. These conditional checks have been positioned in the timing rule to be used to determine the manner of weight changes (potentiation or depression) which has been designed to occur in the timing rule. This can then be used in simulation files to direct the weight changes to target synapses when defining plastic connections.

Figure 75: A flow diagram charting the execution flow of key aspects of the proposed learning rule. Notable changes are calculating a neuron current difference from received excitatory inputs and conditional check for current difference (greater or less than zero)

5.5.7 Challenging aspects of design

Due to the novelty of the design approach as being a first implementation on the SpiNNaker platform, an overarching issue is the unknown data accessing capabilities of SpiNNaker. The reason this being that at the present time, little to no existing research on the implementation of this specific learning rule on neuromorphic hardware. Currently, the neuron state update operations appear to be separate from synaptic operations apart from when the neuron receives the processed inputs in a feed-forward nature. The gap in knowledge manifests itself in the following implications:

Accessing a third voltage quantity from plasticity operations

While it appears straight forward to introduce a new quantity at the neuron model, it is not known whether the memory architecture of the system supports a third quantity to be *accessed* from a different part of SpiNNaker in spike processing. This is critical for the algorithm to function according to its design as the timing rule needs to be able to retrieve the membrane voltage current difference

for a specified neuron ID. The lack of a global memory is particularly restrictive in achieving this. Fundamental changes to the design foreseen to take place if this functionality is not supported on SpiNNaker. This will involve retrieving the input currents from the synaptic input buffers and performing the calculation in the timing rules as previously discussed.

Determining weight changes based on current difference

Another challenging aspect is determining how plastic weights should be changed based on a third voltage quantity, representing a fundamental difference from the standard STDP implementation. This again has not been attempted before on SpiNNaker and it is unknown whether it can be realised on the current hardware implementation. If this is not possible, a more substantial reworking of the timing rule will be required. This will involve modifying the conditions around when synapse potentiation and depression occurs by introducing new conditions that still factor in the pre-post spike timings. As suggested by the reasons above, these potential challenges are difficult to fully foresee at this stage but prior consideration at the design stage will ensure that swift action can be taken to manoeuvre around limitations posed by the sPyNNaker architecture.

6.0 Implementation

This section will elaborate upon the third stage of implementation introduced at the beginning of the design chapter, which is implementing the proposed changes.

- Stage 1: Create test case
- Stage 2: API enhancements
- Stage 3: experimentation and analysis

6.1 Create neuron model test case

To implement the solution, the neuron model template provided by the SpiNNaker development team was used. To create the test case, heavy use of the existing sPyNNaker API components were used. The reason for this implementation choice is to provide a solid and stable test case to ensure that the proposed enhancements function as intended.

6.1.1 C model build

However, these components were combined. The following is the make file created for the test case neuron build accomplishes this.

```
1 APP = $(notdir $(CURDIR))
2 BUILD_DIR = build/
3
4 NEURON_MODEL = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/models/neuron_model_lif_impl.c
5 NEURON_MODEL_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/models/neuron_model_lif_impl.h
6 INPUT_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/input_types/input_type_current.h
7 THRESHOLD_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/threshold_types/threshold_type_static.h
8 SYNAPSE_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/synapse_types/synapse_types_dual_excitatory_exponential_impl.h
9 SYNAPSE_DYNAMICS = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/plasticity/synapse_dynamics_static_impl.c
10
11 include ../Makefile.common
12
```

Figure 76: Test LIF dual exponential synapse neuron C build.

The “SOURCE_DIR” was used to refer to the filepath where the sPyNNaker C API files are located so the neuron components can be accessed from the neuron model template.

6.1.2 Python model build

Similarly, the corresponding python models of each component in the make file was used which included python implementations for:

- The neuron model component
- Input type component
- Synapse type
- Threshold type
- Synapse dynamics

These parts apart from the synapse dynamics were combined in a python build file which specifies the parameters, components to be used and the C executable ‘.aplx’ file to be used for the neuron model. Synapse dynamics, which refers to STDP is instantiated within simulation files because it is an event driven mechanism as opposed to the time-driven mechanism that a neuron model build employs. It’s usage concerned with weight changes between the *connections* of synapses, rather than the synapses itself and therefore is not needed in a Python build file.

1. Importing API Components

API components that are to be used in the build file are first imported.

AbstractPopulationVertex

```
from spynnaker.pyNN.models.neuron.abstract_population_vertex \
    import AbstractPopulationVertex
```

AbstractPopulationVertex is the main interface from which all neuron models must inherit from. This is because it provides access the relevant sPyNNaker related tools and utilities including PACMAN and SpiNNFrontEndcommon APIs that provide the infrastructure to enable the neuron to be simulated on the SpiNN-3 board.

Neuron model component

```
from spynnaker.pyNN.models.neuron.neuron_models.\
    neuron_model_leaky_integrate_and_fire \
    import NeuronModelLeakyIntegrateAndFire
```

Input type

```
from spynnaker.pyNN.models.neuron.input_types.input_type_current \
    import InputTypeCurrent
```

Synapse type

```
from spynnaker.pyNN.models.neuron.synapse_types.synapse_type_dual_exponential \
    import SynapseTypeDualExponential
```

Threshold type

```
from spynnaker.pyNN.models.neuron.threshold_types.threshold_type_static \
    import ThresholdTypeStatic
```

2. Assigning neuron parameters

- Default values

In the case where the end user has not specified and parameters to be used in experiments these values will be used instead. This is assigned to the variable 'default_parameters' as a dictionary consisting of key-value pairs analogous to a hash table.

```
default_parameters = {
    'v_thresh': -50.0, 'tau_syn_E': 5.0, 'tau_syn_E2': 5.0, 'tau_syn_I': 5.0,
    'i_offset': 0, 'tau_m': 32, 'v_init': -80, 'v_rest': -65,
    'v_reset': -95, 'tau_refrac': 5, 'cm': 1.0}
```

Next the parameters are initialised to instantiate a neuron instance that uses this build.

```
def __init__(
    self, n_neurons, spikes_per_second=None, ring_buffer_sigma=None,
    incoming_spike_buffer_size=None, constraints=None, label=None,
```

The “__init__” function is used for initialisation PyNN will look for this method when creating new instances of my test case neuron. The assignments that follow correspond to components in **AbstractPopulationVertex** needed to set up a simulation. These parameters are set as shown since they will be initialised by the super class (**AbstractPopulationVertex**).

However the python components must be overridden to utilise the components declared in the C model Makefile.

Firstly neuron parameters are assigned to specific keys of the dictionary:

```
# neuron model parameters
tau_m=default_parameters['tau_m'], cm=default_parameters['cm'],
v_rest=default_parameters['v_rest'],
v_reset=default_parameters['v_reset'],
tau_refrac=default_parameters['tau_refrac'],
i_offset=default_parameters['i_offset'],

# threshold types parameters
v_thresh=default_parameters['v_thresh'],

tau_syn_E=default_parameters['tau_syn_E'],
tau_syn_E2=default_parameters['tau_syn_E2'],
tau_syn_I=default_parameters['tau_syn_I'],
```

3. Initialising components

This step initialises components so they can be used to create a new instance of **AbstractPopulationVertex**.

First components are instantiated in python:

Neuron model component

```
neuron_model = NeuronModelLeakyIntegrateAndFire(
    n_neurons, v_init, v_rest, tau_m, cm, i_offset,
    v_reset, tau_refrac)
```

Input type

```
input_type = InputTypeCurrent()
```

Synapse type

```
synapse_type = SynapseTypeDualExponential(
    n_neurons, tau_syn_E, tau_syn_E2, tau_syn_I)
```

Threshold type

```
threshold_type = ThresholdTypeStatic(n_neurons, v_thresh)
```

4. Instantiating AbstractPopulationVertex

The purpose of this step is to instantiate the neuron model components with **AbstractPopulationVertex**. This could be considered the main purpose of the python build file and is unique to the sPyNNaker API. First Standard inputs are assigned:

```

AbstractPopulationVertex.__init__(
    # standard inputs, do not need to change.
    self, n_neurons=n_neurons, label=label,
    spikes_per_second=spikes_per_second,
    ring_buffer_sigma=ring_buffer_sigma,
    incoming_spike_buffer_size=incoming_spike_buffer_size,

```

The neuron model instances are configured:

```

# These are the various model types
neuron_model=neuron_model, input_type=input_type,
synapse_type=synapse_type, threshold_type=threshold_type,
additional_input=additional_input,

```

A model name is assigned. This is used in reports for debugging purposes. The binary executable is specified and ensures that the neuron instances uses the components specified in the C model Makefile.

```

# TODO: Give the model a name (shown in reports)
model_name="MyTestCaseModel",

# TODO: Set this to the matching binary name
binary="my_test_model_curr_dual_exp.aplx")

```

Testing the output

To test the output I created an experiment that measures membrane voltage in response to external stimulation which will be elaborated upon in more detail in the upcoming experimentation and evaluation chapter. This was successful and confirms a suitable test case by which to compare the API enhancements that will be made.

6.2 Pyramidal neuron model

After creating and verifying the successful operation of the test case model, the extension of functionality to existing API components will be shown in further detail.

Creating the Makefile

I created a copy of the neuron and synapse type components in the neuron model template and renamed them to distinguish them from the original API files. This is shown in the make file for the enhanced model.

```

APP = $(notdir $(CURDIR))
BUILD_DIR = build/

NEURON_MODEL = $(EXTRA_SRC_DIR)/neuron/models/my_neuron_model_lif_impl.c
NEURON_MODEL_H = $(EXTRA_SRC_DIR)/neuron/models/my_neuron_model_lif_impl.h
INPUT_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/input_types/input_type_current.h
THRESHOLD_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/threshold_types/threshold_type_static.h
SYNAPSE_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/synapse_types/synapse_types_dual_excitatory_exponential_my_impl.h
SYNAPSE_DYNAMICS = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/plasticity/synapse_dynamics_static_impl.c

include ../Makefile.common

```

Figure 77: Pyramidal neuron C build.

6.2.1 API enhancements

This section will detail the API enhancements made down to the code level.

Synapse_types_dual_excitatory_impl.h

In the original API file, the accessor combined the two excitatory inputs so the neuron model could not distinguish the source of the constituent inputs.

A modification that was made was to separate and prevent the inputs being added together, instead implementing accessors for each individual excitatory input.

This was a crucial step as it allowed the excitatory input to be accessed independently of the other excitatory input. I achieved a separation in how the excitatory inputs are accessed.

Implemented changes:

```
static inline input_t synapse_types_get_excitatory_input(
    input_t *input_buffers, index_t neuron_index) {
    return input_buffers[_ex1_offset(neuron_index)];
}

static inline input_t synapse_types_get_excitatory_input2(
    input_t *input_buffers, index_t neuron_index) {
    return input_buffers[_ex2_offset(neuron_index)];
}
```

Figure 78: Code enhancements to synapse type. Adapted from (Stokes and Rowley, 2017¹).

Neuron_model_lif_impl.c

The neuron state update method was identified to be modified since it received the excitatory inputs to calculate the membrane voltage at each timestep. Prior to any enhancements the method received one excitatory input and one inhibitory input from the synapse type.

Another excitatory input (exc_input) was added as a parameter to the method and used in the calculation for the total input at the current timestep. This possessed the same input type (input_t) to enable type compatibility when calculating “input_t input_this_timestep”.

```
state_t neuron_model_state_update(
    input_t exc_input, input_t exc_input2, input_t inh_input, input_t external_bias,
    neuron_pointer_t neuron) {

    // If outside of the refractory period
    if (neuron->refract_timer <= 0) {

        // Get the input in nA
        input_t input_this_timestep =
            exc_input + exc_input2 - inh_input + external_bias + neuron->I_offset;

        _lif_neuron_closed_form(
            neuron, neuron->V_membrane, input_this_timestep);
    } else {

        // countdown refractory timer
        neuron->refract_timer -= 1;
    }
    return neuron->V_membrane;
}
```

Figure 79: Code enhancements for neuron model. Adapted from (Rowley, 2015³).

Changes that were not needed include the header file `neuron_model_lif_impl.h` since its primary purpose is to define the neuron parameters. I wasn't changing any neuron parameters so the file stayed as is.

Enhancements to supporting API files

The following are enhancements to other API file that enable the neuron model changes to function.

`neuron_model.h`

I added the "exc_input2" to the `neuron_model_state_update` function prototype since `Neuron_model_lif_impl.c` includes `neuron_model.h`. This ensures that the parameters in the method signature and function definition match to avoid errors at compile time.

Implemented modifications:

```
state_t neuron_model_state_update(  
    input_t exc_input, input_t exc_input2, input_t inh_input, input_t external_bias,  
    neuron_pointer_t neuron);
```

Figure 80: Code enhancement to `neuron_model.h`. Adapted from (Rowley, 2015²).

`Synapse_types.h`

This change was similar in nature to `neuron_model.h` by adding a method signature to `synapse_types.h` to avoid compile errors. The result is that the function prototype and definition match.

Implemented modifications:

```
static input_t synapse_types_get_excitatory_input2(  
    input_t *input_buffers, index_t neuron_index);
```

Figure 81: Method signature modification for `synapse_type.h`. Adapted from (Stokes and Rowley 2017²).

`Neuron.c`

Additional input processing was implemented to current inputs for `exc_input2`. Below shows the code that retrieves the next value in the excitatory synapse for a neuron and the `neuron_index`. This uses the "synapse_types_get_excitatory_input2" method implemented earlier.

```
input_t exc_input_value2 = input_type_get_input_value(  
    synapse_types_get_excitatory_input2(input_buffers, neuron_index),  
    input_type);
```

Figure 82: Adaptions to `neuron.c`. Original source: (Stokes, Rowley and Davis, 2017).

Additional code was added to process the retrieved value and convert it into a current to be passed to the neuron model through the `neuron_model_state_update` method.

```
input_t exc_input2 = input_type_convert_excitatory_input_to_current(  
    exc_input_value2, input_type, voltage);
```

Figure 83: Adaptions to neuron.c. Original source: (Stokes, Rowley and Davis, 2017).

The neuron_model_state_update() method call was modified to include the new “exc_input2” value. This was done to match the data types of parameters with neuron_model.h and Neuron_model_lif_impl.c and avoid compile and runtime errors resulting from a mis-matching of the order of data types.

```
// update neuron parameters
state_t result = neuron_model_state_update(
    exc_input, exc_input2, inh_input, external_bias, neuron);
```

Figure 84: Adaptions to neuron state update call in neuron.c. Original source: (Stokes, Rowley and Davis, 2017).

6.2.2 Problems encountered during implementation

During implementation of the API enhancements, I encountered a couple of setbacks that delayed implementation progress.

6.2.2.1 Problems with the programming environment

Early on in the implementation process I encountered errors when testing my code. One such problem was the following error shown by the screen capture:

```
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "C:\Users\Justin\OneDrive\FINAL_YEAR\FYP\NeuronModelling\test\examples\my_example.py", line 132, in <module>
    p.run(run_time)
  File "c:\users\justin\onedrive\final_year\fyp\spinnaker\spinnaker\spinnaker\pyNN\__init__.py", line 179, in run
    _spinnaker.run(run_time)
  File "c:\users\justin\onedrive\final_year\fyp\spinnaker\spinnaker\spinnaker\pyNN\spinnaker.py", line 379, in run
    SpinnakerMainInterface.run(self, run_time)
  File "c:\users\justin\onedrive\final_year\fyp\spinnaker\spinnfrontendcommon\spinn_front_end_common\interface\spinnaker_main_interface.py", line 611, in run
    self._do_run(step)
  File "c:\users\justin\onedrive\final_year\fyp\spinnaker\spinnfrontendcommon\spinn_front_end_common\interface\spinnaker_main_interface.py", line 1204, in _do_run
    self._config.get("Reports", "extract_iobuf_from_cores"),
  File "C:\Python27\lib\ConfigParser.py", line 340, in get
    raise NoOptionError(option, section)
ConfigParser.NoOptionError: No option 'extract_iobuf_from_cores' in section: 'Reports'
```

Figure 85: Iobuf error with programming environment.

Along with a mangled development install where I had to re-install the development, the API developers also missed an important Git merge that supported the extraction of IOBUF from the SpiNNaker board in between runs of PyNN scripts. This was done to stop IOBUF being flooded with memory and causing crashes of the SpiNNaker cores. Diagnosing this issue took much effort but fortunately this issue was solved quickly by using a diffident Git branch of the sPyNNaker API named “iobuf_extraction” that included the missing merges. From this I learnt the correct way to setting up a programming environment for development on SpiNNaker as I didn’t do this correctly the first time round. This was due to the complexity of the technology and experiencing for the first time.

Fixing a bug in the neuron template code

When acquainting myself with the existing code provided by the template to implement the test case neuron model I encountered the error below when attempting to compile the example model (full stack trace included in appendix 1):

```
2017-02-26 00:50:42 ERROR: Error executing data specification for 0, 0,
2
Traceback (most recent call last):
...
data_specification.exceptions.DataSpecificationNoMoreException: Space
unavailable to write all the elements requested by the write operation.
Space available: 0; space requested: 4 for region 1.
```

Figure 86: DataSpecification Error when running neuron models.

The bug that caused error was a disagreement on the number of parameters declared in the C code and the python code of the neuron component:

C code:

```
typedef struct neuron_t {
    // TODO: Parameters - make sure these match with the python code,
    // including the order of the variables when returned by
    // get_neural_parameters.

    // Variable-state parameters e.g. membrane voltage
    REAL V;

    // offset current [nA]
    REAL I_offset;

    // Put anything else you want to store per neuron
    REAL my_parameter;
} neuron_t;
```

Figure 87: neuron struct (Rowley, 2016¹).

Python code:

```
def get_n_neural_parameters(self):
    # TODO: update to match the number of parameters
    # Note: this must match the number of parameters in the neuron_t
    # data structure in the C code
    return 1
```

Figure 88: A mis-match in C and python parameters (Rowley, 2016²)

The above should not return 1, since there are 3 neural parameters which caused the error above. I found a similar instance for the threshold component:

C code:

```

6  typedef struct threshold_type_t {
7
8      // TODO: Add any additional parameters here
9
10     REAL threshold_value;
11
12     REAL my_param;
13
14 } threshold_type_t;

```

Figure 89: Threshold type static struct (Rowley, 2015⁴).

Python code:

```

def get_n_threshold_parameters(self):

    # TODO: update to return the number of parameters
    # Note: This must match the number of values in the threshold_type_t
    # data structure in the C code
    return 1

```

Figure 90: Theshold_type_static.py (Rowley and Stokes, 2017⁴)

I created a fork of this repository and changed the values so both get_n_x_parameters methods return the correct number of specified parameters which was recognised and promptly fixed by the API developers for the next version.

Figure 91: Git commit changes to fix bug in sPyNNakerNewModelTemplate module.

6.3 The Urbanczik-Senn plasticity rule

6.3.1 Introducing a current difference

This involved defining a new variable in the existing `neuron_pointer_t` struct with the neuron parameters. The design phase assumed that the current difference would be a decimal value which meant the `REAL` data type was used initially. This was later changed to “`input_t`” as it was discovered that the `input_t` data is used as an abbreviation of the type “`REAL`” in `Neuron_typedefs.h`. This allowed the variable to remain consistent with the `exc_input` and `exc_input2` as they are both of type `input_t`.

```
// The type of an input
typedef REAL input_t;
```

Figure 92: The alias of `input_t` is just `REAL`.

```
input_t current_difference;
```

Figure 93: `input_t` current difference variable.

The current difference calculation is a simple sum placed inside the `neuron_model_state_update()` method and is assigned to the current difference variable. The accessor method of type `input_t` takes the neuron struct and returns the current difference variable. This will be used later when the timing rule requires access to the neuron variables.

```
neuron->current_difference = exc_input - exc_input2;
```

Figure 94: The current difference calculation

```
input_t getcurrentdifference(neuron_pointer_t neuron) {
    return neuron->current_difference;
}
```

Figure 95: The accessor method to obtain the current difference.

In initial debugging, the current difference is recognised when simulating with one neuron. The experiment that was used consisting of spike trains being applied to each synapse to update the neuron model state. The expected result for success is whether the current difference was recognised and calculated.

```

Ring Buffer at 30
-----|
[DEBUG] (synapses.c: 122): Inputs
[DEBUG] (synapses.c: 133): -----
[DEBUG] (synapses.c: 140): 0: 0.814423 (=
0.814423 + 0.000000 - 0.000000[DEBUG] (synapses.c: 142): )
[DEBUG] (synapses.c: 145): -----
[DEBUG] (my_neuron_model_lif_impl.c: 28): current_difference = 0.814423
[DEBUG] (neuron.c: 335): neuron 0 spiked at time 30
[DEBUG] (neuron.c: 87): -----
[DEBUG] (my_neuron_model_lif_impl.c: 67): V membrane = -95.0000 mv
[DEBUG] (neuron.c: 91): -----
[DEBUG] (c_main.c: 198): Timer tick 31

```

Figure 96: Debug log

From the above debug log, the current difference can be seen and appears to have the correct value. At this particular stage in debugging the only the EXCITATORY_ONE synapse is receiving input leaving the EXCITATORY_TWO and INHIBITORY synapses with zero input.

6.3.4 Practical considerations

There were a number of difficulties encountered in the implementation phase of the learning rule which prevented the implementation and testing of the learning rule regarding retrieving current difference in timing rule and determining weight changes. During the course of overcoming managing and overcoming these difficulties the scope of implementing the learning rule became no longer feasible due to time constraints. The following is a discussion of the various issues faced and how implementation of the neuron and learning rule had been impacted.

6.3.4.1 Complexity of existing software

An overriding issue throughout design and implementation stages was the unconventional nature of the sPyNNaker software and supporting API's. This was most clearly evidenced in the use and relationship of C and python code in running simulations. Heavy use of Makefiles to compile C code, advanced functions in header files and custom type definitions all added to architectural complexity. In addition at the time of writing, the lack of suitable documentation on the schematics of operations in SpiNNaker presented a challenge to acquiring a sufficient understanding of important processes. This was most apparent when understanding the current STDP implementation, how neuron models are stimulated. Documentation did exist, but only in the form explanations of functions which was found lacking as it did not go into detail on how the functions worked together to bring about important processes such as the updating of synaptic weights. The lack of suitable tutorials and example code meant that implementation was often a discovery process of trial-and-error. This meant that a disproportional amount of time was spent understanding how different API parts used each other to identify suitable designs and implementation of the neuron model and learning rule.

Perhaps a reason for this is due to the newness of the technology, having only been made available for non-expert use in the last several years. Experts would only need to use the API at a high level and do not need to understand the API at a low level.

To address these challenges exiting source code and any accompanying comments were extensively examined to piece together how synapses, neuron state updates and STDP functioned which was

greatly time consuming. However the process of information gathering was sped up by making use of the “SpiNNaker Users Group” online forum to facilitate direct communication to SME research partners that develop the underlying software.

6.3.4.2 Delays in responses

The “SpiNNaker Users Group” enabled more timely verification and clarification to develop knowledge of the existing architecture, especially when problems arose during implementation when partners responded. However, a disadvantage of this method was when responses were slow or delayed which were critical for progress. This prolonged the time it took to solve issues and had a negative effect on the existing time constraints of the project, prompting the postponement of certain activates. This combined with the lack of complete developer documentation and the uniqueness of the technology at the time of writing meant that timely progress was often reliant on the responses of research partners especially when troubleshooting issues in the underlying software and discussing implementation feasibility.

A small number of partners were active on the forum for much of the project duration. To overcome this limitation, other knowledgeable partners were sought out to ask questions. This enabled timelier response times when the SpiNNaker Users Group were unresponsive to queries.

When faced with response delays, one-to-one discussions were organised with the project supervisor to examine source code and develop understanding of various data flows of processes in the system. This was also beneficial as it developed deeper understanding of the underlying source code that could be matched to high level descriptions of data flows given by research partners. But this process was time consuming which delayed implementation and evaluation stages since the project supervisor was not an SME on the sPyNNaker architecture but was knowledgeable in computational neuroscience. They provided insight into why certain functions were defined to adhere to biological principles.

6.3.4.3 Difficulties with programming environment

Perhaps when the complexity of the SpiNNaker software and the delays in responses was most apparent was when the development environment became corrupted in some way. A prior instance of this was elaborated upon in Section 6.2.2 which happened in the middle stages of the project. Unfortunately, when implementing aspects of the learning rule that it was advised that local Git repositories for all SpiNNaker modules were updated to the Master branch to avoid compatibility issues. This resulted in a corruption of the programming environment.

```
Traceback (most recent call last):
...
File
"c:\users\justin\onedrive\final_year\fyp\spinnaker\spinnfrontendcommon\spinn_fr
ont_end_common\interface\interface_functions\front_end_common_chip_runtime_upda
ter.py", line 24, in __call__
    executable_targets.all_core_subsets, app_id, [CPUState.PAUSED])
File
"c:\users\justin\onedrive\final_year\fyp\spinnaker\spinnman\spinnman\transceive
r.py", line 2077, in wait_for_cores_to_be_in_state
    error_cores, cpu_state))
spinnman.exceptions.SpinmanException: 52 cores have reached an error state
CPUState.RUN_TIME_EXCEPTION:
```

Figure 97: An error indicating that the system crashed during runtime.

On further investigation, the cause of this issue was a new module name SpiNNUtils which added further utility classes and functions essential for SpiNNaker development. A re-install of the software that included this module was completed and a re-compile of all C modules was attempted which resulted in the following error:

```
make[1]: Entering directory
`/home/Justin/OneDrive/FINAL_YEAR/FYP/SpiNNaker/sPyNNaker/neural_modelling/src/spike_source/poisson'
make[1]: *** No rule to make target
`/c/Users/Justin/OneDrive/FINAL_YEAR/FYP/SpiNNaker/sPyNNaker/spynnaker/pyNN/model_binaries/spike_sour
ce_poisson.aplx', needed by `all'. Stop.
make[1]: Leaving directory
`/home/Justin/OneDrive/FINAL_YEAR/FYP/SpiNNaker/sPyNNaker/neural_modelling/src/spike_source/poisson'
make: *** [all] Error 2
```

Figure 98: Compile error due to not being able to find spike_source_poisson.aplx. This was unexpected as the file could be located in a directory but could not be found by the linker.

To solve the error, multiple re-installs of the development tools were attempted as troubleshooting steps which could not solve the problem. Reverting to the iobuf_extraction branch that fixed the first instance of this problem was not possible since it had been deleted.

The unconventional installation process for the tools was particularly time consuming with many parts involved. Following consultation with research partners it was decided a switch to an Ubuntu environment would be set up to install the SpiNNaker build tools. The initial compile of the tools were successful but additional errors were faced when compiling the make file in “/c_models/src/neuron” in the neuron model template code to build each neuron model.

Again, delays in responses were experienced when communicating the errors to research partners which hindered progress. It was revealed that additional bugs present in makefile.common caused this error in compilation. Switching to the update_models branch for the SpyNNakerNewModelTemplate API module solved compilation and runtime errors. More specifically, makefile.common corrected the relative file paths so that “python_models/model_binaries/” and “EXTRA_SRC_DIR” (set to c_models/src) could be located.

Below is a comparison between makefile.common from the master branch and the same file from the “update_models” branch. Main differences have been highlighted in red.

```
MAKEFILE_PATH := $(abspath $(lastword $(MAKEFILE_LIST)))
CURRENT_DIR := $(dir $(MAKEFILE_PATH))
EXTRA_SRC_DIR := $(abspath $(CURRENT_DIR))
SOURCE_DIRS += $(EXTRA_SRC_DIR)
APP_OUTPUT_DIR := $(abspath $(CURRENT_DIR)../../python_models/model_binaries/)
CFLAGS += -I$(NEURAL_MODELLING_DIRS)/src
```

Figure 99: Makefile.common found in SpyNNakerNewModelTemplate Master branch that specifies general make rules that apply to all neuron builds (Rowley, 2016³).

```
MAKEFILE_PATH := $(abspath $(lastword $(MAKEFILE_LIST)))
CURRENT_DIR := $(dir $(MAKEFILE_PATH))
EXTRA_SRC_DIR := $(abspath $(CURRENT_DIR))/../..
SOURCE_DIRS += $(EXTRA_SRC_DIR)
APP_OUTPUT_DIR := $(abspath $(CURRENT_DIR)/../..../python_models/model_binaries/)
CFLAGS += -I$(NEURAL_MODELLING_DIRS)/src
```

Figure 100: Makefile.common in “update_models” branch fixes compilation errors by correcting the file paths. The branch has since been deleted from SpyNNakerNewModelTemplate.

6.3.4.4 Difficulties with test case

As a preliminary test case to assess the capabilities of synaptic models on SpiNNaker, an existing test script was used. This consisted of an STDP experiment that utilised the IF_curr_exp neuron build and was replaced with the IF_curr_dual_Exp neuron for testing purposes. The implemented neuron that distinguished between two inputs was based on IF_curr_dual_Exp build which used the leaky integrate and fire neuron and dual excitatory synapse components. Therefore, it was thought that the results from this neuron build would serve as a test case against which to judge the results from the Urbanczik-Senn rule.

The following changes were made achieve this outcome.

```
model = sim.IF_curr_dual_exp

cell_params= {'tau_m': 20.0, 'cm': 1.0, 'v_rest': -65.0, 'v_reset': -65.0, 'v_thresh': -50.0, 'tau_syn_E': 5.0,
'tau_syn_E2': 5.0, 'tau_syn_I': 5.0, 'tau_refrac': 0.1, 'i_offset': 0}
```

Figure 101: Changes to use IF_curr_dual_exp – the model and the parameters corresponding to the neuron and synapse type parameters are required.

Initial test runs did not behave as expected where the following shows the main error:

```
File
"c:\users\justin\onedrive\final_year\fyf\spinnaker\spinnfrontendcommon\spinn
n_front_end_common\interface\interface_functions\front_end_common_graph_bin
ary_gatherer.py", line 49, in _get_binary
    raise exceptions.ExecutableNotFoundException(binary_name)
spinn_front_end_common.utilities.exceptions.ExecutableNotFoundException:
IF_curr_exp_dual_stdp_mad_nearest_pair_additive.aplx
```

Figure 102: STDP model error - could not find the C executable.

The error indicated that the appropriate executable was not found which meant that it did not currently exist in the sPyNNaker architecture alongside pre-built models.

As an attempt to solve this, a new makefile was created to construct a build with the appropriate components. It was then named the file name that was expected by the error, “IF_curr_exp_dual_stdp_mad_nearest_pair_additive” and placed in the builds directory

to be accessed by API calls. This led to another error when running the test simulation with this model.

```
File
"c:\users\justin\onedrive\final_year\fyp\spinnaker\pacman\pacman\executor\pacman_algorithm_executor.py", line 221, in _get_algorithm_data
    "Cannot find algorithm {}".format(algorithm_name))
pacman.exceptions.PacmanConfigurationException: Cannot find algorithm
FrontEndCommonIOBufExtractor
```

Figure 103: An error encountered when running the existing STDP example script with the IF_curr_dual_exp using the "IF_curr_exp_dual_stdp_mad_nearest_pair_additive.aplx" binary.

Initial communication with research partners about this error suggested that this model had not been tested and was not supported on SpiNNaker currently. But after an extensive analysis of the setup a bug was found in the make file that pointed to an incorrect file path for the plasticity mechanism. This was corrected and the model could then be used in the test script.

The time spent solving the errors in the programming environment and the test case pushed the implementation of the learning rule beyond feasibility, given the project time constraints and meant that code was not able to be debugged. This was an unforeseen difficulty where lack of clear documentation on troubleshooting synaptic models led to large delays fixing minor bugs as help was limited to emailing on the SpiNNaker User Group forum.

7.0 Results and evaluation of outputs

This chapter will focus on the experiments that were conducted to verify the operation of the test case neuron and the pyramidal neuron build with my enhancements to extend the functionality of the sPyNNaker API.

7.1 Experimental focus

Before designing the experiments to evaluate the neuron model, it is important to determine the focus on the results that should be seen. This will enable the correct experimentation to be designed to accurately verify the pyramidal model that has been created from API enhancements. The following outline the chosen experiments to verify neuron model behaviour.

1. The change in membrane voltage over time.

A standard experiment is to stimulate a neuron model at timed intervals to evaluate its behaviour. This will be realised by an experiment measuring the response of a neuron model to synaptic input. This will be a good experiment to conduct since we can not only evaluate when the neuron will spike, but how it resets and decays back to its original membrane potential. Specific synapses can be stimulated to assess their impact behaviour on neuron stimulation to verify if its expected behaviour.

For the proposed experiment this will consist of an input spike train connected as a 'dummy' neuron for each synapse of the test neuron. The experiment will be repeated on the pyramidal neuron and the results compared.

This could be represented visually as:

Figure 104: A visual representation of the proposed experimental focus. Target spike trains will be applied to each synapse (Excitatory one, excitatory 2, inhibitory) to test correct functionality.

An inhibitory (Inh) and two excitatory synapses (Exc1 and Exc2) are represented as arrows feeding input to the soma analogous to dendrites. The soma will determine if the combined input depolarises (increase membrane potential) or hyperpolarises (decrease) the neuron membrane potential (output).

Each spike train will be inputted with differing timings to allow the resulting graph to highlight clearly the behaviour of the neuron synapses. What should therefore be seen is a depolarisation in the neuron in response to excitatory input and hyperpolarisation in response to inhibitory input.

2. Spiking operation over time

This will be realised through a spike raster plot, realised through a spike train emitted from the neuron being stimulated. An experiment like this offers a different perspective on the behaviour of the neuron model, concentrating only on the spiking output rather than the fluctuations of membrane potential outline in the previous experimental focus. It will also enable the identification of patterns on spikes due to a stimulus or network activity over time. This can be important to verify if synaptic plasticity is observed within populations of neurons.

Sometimes it is difficult to tell when a neuron has spiked by focusing on the change in membrane voltage over time. Looking at output spike trains will allow us to evaluate if the neuron is operating correctly under conditions that should generate a spike.

Since the experiment will utilise spike trains, any resulting out spikes from the stimulated neuron can be recorded and saved to an array. Matplotlib will use the array to plot any spikes that occurred against time.

Justification of chosen experiments

Both of the experimental focuses on a fundamental objective to verify that the pyramidal neuron has been successfully implemented: that no stimulation is lost from the injecting of external current to the neuron output. This will be achieved by comparing the model with the behaviour of the test case neuron. If both results are the same by means of visual inspection, then it can be concluded that the API enhancements were accepted by the API and would confirm that no synaptic input was lost by separating the way excitatory inputs were accessed and passed to the `neuron_model_state_update` method. This conclusion will be sufficient for success as it will confirm that the neuron can distinguish between two excitatory inputs at each time step with no loss.

7.2 Experiment design

Importing components

First important API such as `pylab` and `SpiNNaker PyNN` are important to access functions of the API. Importantly the neuron model build will be used in this experiment.

```
import pylab

import spynnaker.pyNN as p

from python_models.neuron.builds.my_model_curr_dual_exp import
MyModelCurrDualExp
```

Assigning parameters

The following parameters were specified:

```
# Set the run time of the execution
run_time = 600

# Set the time step of the simulation in
milliseconds
time_step = 1.0

# Set the number of neurons to simulate
n_neurons = 1

# Set the i_offset current
i_offset = 0.0

# Set the weight of input spikes
weight_exc1 = 2.0
weight_exc2 = 10.0
weight_inh = 5.0
```

Runtime: This is measured in milliseconds and set to 600 to allow sufficient time to input three different spike trains spaced out in time.

Timestep: set to 1 millisecond to be consistent with the standard timestep used for neuron simulations

N_neurons: refers to the number of neurons to be simulated and is set to 1. For the preliminary experiment this will enable more precise results.

I_offset: this refers to an additional bias current to drive up the membrane potential of the neuron to make it spike. This has been set to zero because the focus is to assess behaviour the synapses through directly applied inputs and including an offset might contaminate the results.

Weight parameters: refers to the strength of each synaptic connection to the synapse. Three different weights are specified to visualise differing effects of weights on synapses. With the values specified, it is expected that inputs to the exc1 synapse will depolarise the neuron by a small amount and then repolarise back to the resting membrane voltage. With a weight of 10, I expect to see exc2 depolarise the neuron by a large amount – possibly resulting in spikes. A weight of 5.0 will hyperpolarise the neuron and the membrane voltage should decrease.

Creating spike trains

Below are the values specified for the spike train for each synapse. These values were chosen create a clear result on which spike train is being applied by spacing them out in time.

```
spike_times = [25, 50, 80, 100] # excitatory compartment 1
spike_times1 = [180, 210, 240, 270] # excitatory compartment 2
spike_times2 = [400, 430, 460, 490] # inhibitory compartment
```

Create input populations

Here three separate populations are defined each possessing one neuron. These will act as the ‘dummy’ neurons which are configured to stimulate our neuron using the specified spike trains.

```
input_pop = p.Population(  
    1, p.SpikeSourceArray, {"spike_times": spike_times},  
    label="input")  
  
input_pop1 = p.Population(  
    1, p.SpikeSourceArray, {"spike_times": spike_times1},  
    label="input1")  
  
input_pop2 = p.Population(  
    1, p.SpikeSourceArray, {"spike_times": spike_times2},  
    label="input2")
```

Create neuron population

The real neuron population is created using the neuron model build with two parameters, a resting membrane potential (*v_rest*) and an offset bias current (*i_offset*).

```
my_model_pop = p.Population(  
    1, MyModelCurrDualExp,  
    {  
        "v_rest": -70.0,  
        "i_offset": i_offset,  
    },  
    label="my_model_pop")
```

Projections

The connections are created between the input neurons (*input_pop*) and the test neuron *MyModelCurrDualExp* (*my_model_pop*). A *OneToOneConnector* is used to represent the connections in figure with the specified weights for each synapse. Most importantly the target synapse to be stimulated is specified using the “target” attribute to direct the input current.

```
p.Projection(input_pop, my_model_pop, p.OneToOneConnector(weights=weight_exc1,  
    target="excitatory")  
p.Projection(input_pop1, my_model_pop, p.OneToOneConnector(weights=weight_exc2),  
    target="excitatory2")  
p.Projection(input_pop2, my_model_pop, p.OneToOneConnector(weights=weight_inh),  
    target="inhibitory")
```

Record membrane voltage and spikes

Recording for membrane voltage and any output spikes is set up for the test case neuron. This is done by using the “record_v()” and “record()” from the sPyNNaker API.

```
my_model_pop.record_v() # record voltage
my_model_pop.record()   # record spikes
```

Plot graphs

Membrane voltage

A function to gather the membrane voltage through “get_v()” method at each timer tick is defined and the plot is configured.

```
# A function to create a graph of voltage against time
def create_v_graph(population, title):
    v = population.get_v()
    if v is not None:
        ticks = len(v) / n_neurons
        pylab.figure()
        pylab.xlabel('Time (ms)')
        pylab.ylabel("Membrane Voltage")
        pylab.title(title)

        for pos in range(n_neurons):
            v_for_neuron = v[pos * ticks: (pos + 1) * ticks]
            pylab.plot([i[1] for i in v_for_neuron],
                      [i[2] for i in v_for_neuron])
```

The plotting function is called after the simulation has run.

```
create_v_graph(
    my_model_pop, "SpiNNaker Model")

pylab.show() # show the graph
```

Spike raster plot

To plot the spike raster, sPyNNaker allows access to a spike array. Any out spike will be placed in as element which can be used to iteratively plot the spikes times. The “getSpikes()” method enables this functionality.

```
spikes = my_model_pop.getSpikes(compatible_output=True)
```

The following code sets up the graph axes and plot the spikes from the spike array as dots with the “pylab.plot” line.

```
def plot_spikes(spikes, title):
    if spikes is not None:
        pylab.figure()
        pylab.xlim((0, run_time))
        pylab.plot([i[1] for i in spikes], [i[0] for i in spikes], ".")
        pylab.xlabel('Time/ms')
        pylab.ylabel('spikes')
        pylab.title(title)

    else:
        print "No spikes received"
```

Plotting the graph

```
plot_spikes(spikes, "Test model Spike raster plot")
pylab.show()
```

Running the simulation on SpiNNaker

The run() method tells the API to package up the simulation and upload data onto the SpiNNaker board. During the simulation, SpiNNaker is not able to accept any new data in real time and must be specified before or after the simulation. The end() method signifies that the simulation is over and releases memory back to the SpiNNaker system.

```
p.run(run_time)
##Plot membrane voltage graph
## Plot spikes
p.end()
```

7.3 Results

The following figure is the resulting output describing the change in membrane voltage over time for the test case neuron, MyModelCurrDualExp.

Figure 105: The test case neuron output.

The order of spike trains applied to synapses was specified to be:

1. Excitatory 1 (with weight 2.0)
2. Excitatory 2 (with weight 10.0)
3. Inhibitory (with weight 5.0)

By means of visual inspection it is apparent that the spike trains and operation of the neuron has been correctly depicted in the graph.

This is an expected result. For the exc1 synapse, it was foreseen that a weight of 2.0 will depolarise the neuron but would not be strong enough for it to produce spiking output. This is exactly what is seen in the results. There are four 'peaks' of activity between 25-100ms, where the neuron starts to decay back to the resting potential of -70mV. But due to the close timing of the spikes, the neuron was prevented from returning fully back to a resting state.

For the ex2 synapse, there is evidence of spiking activity due to the membrane voltage lowering down to a reset voltage. This behaviour should only occur when a spike has happened. This was expected behaviour as the weight of the synapse was set to a higher value to increase the likelihood of the neuron spiking. What is not expected is the observation that the membrane potential does not reach the threshold set for spiking activity to occur. The threshold parameter "v_thresh" was initially set to -50mV so it is expected that the voltage should reach this number. From the graph it appears that only one of the stimulations reached a peak of -50mV so we should see only one spike. A possible reason behind could be simply due to a limitation of the matplotlib plotting library and not indicative of anomalies in the experiment. Again, due to the close timing of spikes the neuron was not able to repolarise to -70mV, manging this between 300-400ms.

For the inh synapse, what is expected behaviour has been observed from the results – namely four instances of hyperpolarisation. A weight value of 5.0 means the neuron is more likely to decrease in membrane potential by a larger amount.

```
default_parameters = {
    'v_thresh': -50.0, 'tau_syn_E': 5.0, 'tau_syn_E2': 5.0, 'tau_syn_I': 5.0,
    'i_offset': 0, 'tau_m': 32, 'v_init': -80, 'v_rest': -65,
    'v_reset': -95, 'tau_refrac': 5, 'cm': 1.0}
```

Given these observations it can be concluded that the test case model functions as intended. The same experiment can be conducted for the pyramidal neuron for which we should see the same output. The reason for this is that a separation of excitatory inputs was achieved with the API extensions so it is expected that no difference should be observed on how the inputs are received by the neuron soma.

7.3.1 Comparisons and analysis

Figure 106: (a: left) the pyramidal neuron (b: right) the test case neuron output describing membrane voltage over time.

The resulting output labelled “Pyramidal neuron” is the graph for the implemented pyramidal neuron as a compartmental model.

At a first glance, it was a similar output to the test case neuron which is an expected result but there are some differences in how the 2nd excitatory input was handled which was unexpected. This includes:

- Clearer indication of spiking activity
- A faster repolarisation time

In the “SpiNNaker model” graph it was observed that the peaks of the exc2 synapse activity was ambiguous as they did not reach the specified threshold that determined a spike output. However the membrane voltage reset which is indicative of spiking activity. In the “Pyramidal neuron” result this phenomenon is much clearer to see as the spiking activity hits the threshold and possibly goes over, but also corresponds to the voltage reset. We know without doubt that spiking activity has

occurred. But this could likely be due to a limitation of the matplotlib library itself as the main spiking operation has initiated but there are discrepancies when visually plotted.

Another difference was a faster repolarisation from the reset voltage to resting voltage at 70mV in the ex2 synapse. The “SpiNNaker model” could repolarise to -80mV at most in between spikes.

This results were not expected and the API enhancements appear to have changed the dynamics of the neuron. However it is ambiguous why this is the case and could be considered a deficiency of the experiment. The “tau_refract” parameter describes the rate of the refractory period where the neuron returns to a resting potential. The parameter was kept the same in both experiments, which were conducted three times to verify the accuracy of results.

Another set of experiments were conducted to test whether the test case required a faster refractory rate to match the pyramidal neuron.

All variables were kept the same but the ‘tau_refract’ parameter was changed from 5.0 to 1.0. This generated an output that matched the pyramidal neuron.

Figure 107: the output of the experiment measuring membrane potential over time using the sPyNNaker test case -‘tau_refract’ parameter was changed from 5.0 to 1.0.

From the result it can be observed that when the refractory time is set to 1.0, there is a faster reset rate where the membrane potential climbs back fully to the resting membrane voltage at -70 mV. This strengthens the observation made that the refractory time for the pyramidal neuron propagates at a faster rate.

A further experiment conducted on the pyramidal neuron was an increase the refractory time to a slower time scale to assess whether the membrane voltage still reset at a faster rate. If the result show that it did, then it can be concluded that a bug was present when the refractory time was not communicated to the neuron model and perhaps was set to 1.0 as default.

For this experiment the ‘tau_refract’ parameter was set to a higher value of 100 to give clear indication of any issues. If a bug was present, it is expected that the result remains unchanged from

Figure 106a. Otherwise only one spike should be recorded since a high refract time would prevent the voltage retuning to -70mV.

The result that was produced by the experiment shows membrane voltage remaining constant after spiking between 180-270ms in the below figure.

Figure 108: 'tau_refract' parameter was set to a higher value of 100 for the pyramidal neuron to test for any abnormalities.

If there was not a bug, a result showing a constant membrane voltage at the excitatory two synapse for the duration of the spike train should be seen. This is exactly what is seen and is clear indication that the 'tau_refract' parameter has been propagated correctly. This confirms that no bug is present in the neuron code.

Spike raster plots

To further verify the spiking output, a raster plot can be generated for each experiment. The following is a spike raster for the test case experiment.

Figure 109: Spike raster plot for test case neuron.

The blue spots represent spiking output and corresponds to the times when membrane voltage was increased to the threshold. Therefore this confirms that spiking activity did happen and could be a limitation with the plotting software in visually depicting spikes reaching the threshold potential.

The spike raster for the pyramidal neuron shows a similar result which gives further clarification that the neuron model spiking activity is operating correctly.

This comes as a direct result of the changes that were targeted at the exc2 input and clarifies and gives confidence that there has been an enhancement of the API.

7.4 Evaluation

This section will offer a short and necessarily so since a small handful of requirements were implemented. Of the requirements that were implemented, it is straightforward to test by running a simple simulation. What was achieved was to add assessor methods and input type function calls to construct an independent excitatory channel in the existing software architecture of sPyNNaker. The most notable of these changes was to add an `exc_input2` parameter in the `neuron_model_state_update` method, implement accessor methods to obtain only one excitatory input from the input buffers and provide function called in `neuron.c` to process the input before passing to the neuron soma.

From the experiments conducted it can be concluded that the handling of the excitatory inputs has been successfully separated so that the neuron can distinguish between two excitatory inputs. A test case has been constructed consisting of a spike train applied to each synapse. The same experiment using the pyramidal neuron showed no loss of inputs to the synapses where the behaviour was the same.

A key advantage of the pyramidal neuron is the implementation of a new method to distinguish excitatory neuron inputs. The benefit of this new contribution is that it can be used as a test case model for learning rules that rely on an excitatory error signal such as the Urbanczik-Senn rule. The second excitatory channel can as a teaching signal that is independent from the first excitatory channel in order to provide the infrastructure for the learning rule to operate. In general, the state space of the neuron has been increased allowing the neuron model to have access to another

'tuning' variable that can be applied to other neuronal simulations such as modelling pyramidal dendritic behaviour as described in 2.6 Pyramidal neurons.

A shortcoming of the pyramidal neuron model is that it could be considered a highly-simplified model that is reducible to a standard LIF neuron with Dual excitatory synapse. It can be argued that there is no substantial difference in behaviour except the distinguishing of more excitatory inputs when received by the soma. The biological properties of distal and tuft dendrites are unaccounted for which the LIF neuron and the SpiNNaker architecture itself tries to simplify.

A key difference between the two models is the refractory time is slower on the standard LIF implementation. This could have a considerable impact on simulating large networks of pyramidal neurons by resulting in more spiking activity if the 'tau_refract' parameter is set to a low value. Given the limitations and complexity of the existing architecture this is sufficient as a first exploratory step to create compartmental models in SpiNNaker.

Further testing

Further testing that could be conducted to gain further confidence that the pyramidal neuron achieves the distinguishing of more than one excitatory input is to compile the neuron model in debug mode and verify the exc_input2 value in memory. This would empirically confirm that the API enhancements process exc_input2 at the low-level and would supplement visual results to present a more informed conclusion. Due to project time constraints, this test can be carried out as further work beyond this project.

7.5 Other experiments

A further experiment was conducted to achieve the aim of exploring the capabilities of the SpiNNaker simulator in simulating STDP in a network of Izhikevich neurons. As discussed in 2.4.3 Neuron models, Izhikevich neurons strike a balance between biological complexity and computation efficiency. Although not strictly part of the project objectives, this has not been conducted before using the sPyNNaker API and ran on SpiNNaker and will serve as a useful test to achieve the aims of the project.

The experiment will consist of a network of randomly connected neurons analogous to aspects of Izhikevich's experiment in detecting polychronous groups – neural networks that create reproducible time locked firing patterns with millisecond precisions that may not always be synchronous (Izhikevich, 2006). The study attempts to describe how the brain processes information and Izhikevich puts forward the notion that polychronous groups could be the backbone to the formation of memories and even consciousness. The idea is to use an external input source as the 'engine' to initiate spiking activity in the excitatory population after which the network will drive activity. The focus is not to reproduce polychronous groups but the focus of this experiment is to observe the activity of the network in response to input spikes and synaptic plasticity . The key question being, does synaptic plasticity maintain balanced spiking activity of the network?

The network consists of the following tuned parameters:

Model: IZK_curr_exp

```

APP = $(notdir $(CURDIR))
BUILD_DIR = build/

NEURON_MODEL = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/models/neuron_model_izh_impl.c
NEURON_MODEL_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/models/neuron_model_izh_impl.h
INPUT_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/input_types/input_type_current.h
THRESHOLD_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/threshold_types/threshold_type_static.h
SYNAPSE_TYPE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/synapse_types/synapse_types_exponential_impl.h
SYNAPSE_DYNAMICS = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/plasticity/stdp/synapse_dynamics_stdp_mad_impl.c
TIMING_DEPENDENCE = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/plasticity/stdp/timing_dependence/timing_nearest_pair_impl.c
TIMING_DEPENDENCE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/plasticity/stdp/timing_dependence/timing_nearest_pair_impl.h
WEIGHT_DEPENDENCE = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/plasticity/stdp/weight_dependence/weight_additive_one_term_impl.c
WEIGHT_DEPENDENCE_H = $(SOURCE_DIR)/neuron/plasticity/stdp/weight_dependence/weight_additive_one_term_impl.h

include ../Makefile.common

```

Figure 110: The Make file for the IZK_curr_exp model that shows the components used.

Total Population size = 100 (80% excitatory and 20% inhibitory to preserve ratio observed in biology (Braitenberg and Schüz, 1991)).

External input: Spike Source Poisson – random spikes according to a global firing rate.

Simulation time: 2000ms.

Synapse dynamics: SpikePairRule with timing dependence and additive weight dependence.

Connections utilised

Connection 1 - External input to excitatory population: one-to one-connector with weights=16.0 and delays=1.0 targeting excitatory synapses. The weight value is chosen as such to be sufficient to induce spiking activity.

Connection 2 - Inhibitory to excitatory population: Fixed probability connectors with p_connect = 0.1, weights = 5.0 and delays=1.0 (Izhikevich, 2006, pg 275).

Connection 3 - excitatory to inhibitory population: Fixed probability connector with p_connect = 0.1, allow_self_connections =False, weights: 6.0 with synaptic plasticity and random delays (Izhikevich, 2006, pg 275). Excitatory synapses are targeted. Parameters for plastic connections: $\tau_+ = \tau_- = 20$ ms, $A_+ = 0.1$ and $A_- = 0.12$. Mirrors plastic parameters used by Izhikevich (Izhikevich, 2006, pg 252).

Connection 4 - excitatory to excitatory population: Fixed probability connector with similar parameters to connection 3 with no target synapses to direct inputs to. By virtue of the connection, this is already implied.

Figure 111: A diagram presenting the structure of the proposed Izhikevich network simulation.

Figure 110 a visualisation of the network. P_{inh} signifies the inhibitory populations. P_{exc} refers to the excitatory populations. P_{in} refers to the spike source Poisson input. Neurons in this population fire randomly according to the firing rate and each neuron is connected to an excitatory neuron targeting its excitatory synapse. Inhibitory neurons do not have connections with each other but are connected to the neurons in the excitatory population with no plastic connections and a connection probability of 0.1 ($p_{connect}$). Within the excitatory populations, neurons are connected to each other with a probability of 0.1 and are plastic. The same connection is used to connect the excitatory neurons to the inhibitory neurons where in the actual experiment there could be more than one connection and is shown conceptually.

It is envisioned that the results will produce a pattern of activity where there are strong bursts of activity at the beginning due to the constant current input from the external source. A weight value of 16 should be strong enough to excite the excitatory population to fire, inducing plasticity by making the inhibitory and the excitatory neurons fire. This could drive down activity in the network for a short time before increasing in spiking activity in excitatory neurons due to connection 2. This is where targeting the excitatory synapse is important, as this should excite the excitatory population to spike to continue the back and forth excitation of inhibitory and then excitatory neurons.

7.5.1 Results

Figure 112 and Figure 114 show the results of the experiment. Multiple experiments were run (See Appendix A) and there appeared to be a trend with high activity in excitatory neurons at the start of the simulation that starts to settle towards 1000ms (See

Figure 112). This corresponds to what was expected to be seen as the external input has produced large amounts of activity in the excitatory population due to the one-to-one connector used. The inhibitory spikes show activity that follows activity in the excitatory neurons. The result is an

apparent rhythmic pattern that can be seen through columns of spiking activity in both populations due to the random connected nature of the network.

Figure 112: A spike raster plot of the first 0-1000ms for a network of 100 Izhikevich neurons simulated over 2000ms. (left) the excitatory population, (right) the inhibitory population.

A plot of the latter 1000ms presents more expansively the dying down of intense activity shown by Figure 113 between 0 and 200ms. The network starts to settle into a clear rhythmic pattern, and suggests that it is learning the right balance of excitatory and inhibitory activity.

Figure 114: A spike raster plot of the 1000-2000ms for a network of 100 Izhikevich neurons simulated over 2000ms. (left) the excitatory population, (right) the inhibitory population.

To examine this more closely, a comparison is done with the same network but without plastic connections to activate synaptic plasticity in excitatory neurons. All other parameters were kept the same apart from the simulation time which was set to 5000ms to allow ample time for any activity to occur and the result is shown in Figure 115 and Figure 116.

Figure 115: A spike raster plot of 80 excitatory Izhikevich neurons with no plastic connections, simulated over 5000ms.

In Figure 115 the activity in the excitatory population is shown to possess some rhythmic activity at the beginning and have high output towards the end. This is similarly represented in Figure 116 with very high spiking activity. This indicates a very high density of output. This is not expected as more of a rhythmic pattern should have been more apparent. Perhaps a key reason why could be the lack of regulation of spiking activity. There seems to be no delay where there is a constant stream of spikes from both populations from start to finish.

Figure 116: A spike raster plot of 20 inhibitory Izhikevich neurons with no plastic connections, simulated over 5000ms.

The use of the firing rate “ $e_rate = 1000 / N_E$ ” with $N_E = 80$ neurons. This refers to the firing rate of one spike on average every second in hertz. $1 / N_E$ is the input firing rate for spikes per millisecond meaning every 80ms the spike train will constitute one spike which is multiplied by 1000 to convert spikes from milliseconds to seconds (Hz). Another factor that could be important is the weight value of the connection between external input and the excitatory population. A high weight value means the excitatory population will spike more often. Perhaps the unregulated nature of the network is producing the results seen where neuron keep spiking and do not learn a balanced way of behaving.

It can be concluded from these results that STDP is important in regulating and maintaining balanced excitability behaviour in randomly connected network of Izhikevich neurons. This could be due to the timing and weight rules employed by STDP that monitor the network to apply appropriate weight updates in phases.

7.5.2 Difficulties encountered in experimentation

This section will elaborate on some of the issues encountered while implementing the experiment.

Unforeseen API updates

During implementation of the experiment design an issue with the stable technology stack were encountered where the existing programming environment set up created problems with using models correctly. Model builds were compiling but were creating unexpected results. Upon detailed analysis of the current setup, it was revealed that the sPyNNaker API repository was being split by the development team into a sPyNNaker7 repository to remain consistent with PyNN 0.75 and sPyNNaker8 for PyNN 0.8. However, both still used aspects of the 'main' sPyNNaker repository. This mean that some features have been moved to different versions. One example was the timing nearest neighbour was omitted from sPyNNaker7 which meant that the model build for the Izhikevich neuron had to use Timing_pair implementations. This issue arose near to the end of the project and was time consuming to diagnose since there were no prior messages from the development team that these changes were being made and highlights the infancy of the technology. To solve this issue the latest updates from Git repositories of the programming environment were pulled down to maintain compatibility and is a recommended first step to troubleshooting issues with the programming environment.

Simulation times

When simulating more than 100 Izhikevich neurons errors occurred that signalled a system crash. This could be due to the limited technical specifications of the board in terms of processing capacity but also inefficient calibration settings whose optimal settings could not be determined within the project time constraints. This was an unexpected result because the board is able to support up to 256 neurons per core and 200 neurons in total were being simulated. Another error was encountered when simulating 100 neurons for times longer than 2000ms. The configuration file for the SpiNNaker board was modified to increase the machine time step and timescale factor but this resulted in unexpected results. In response only 100 Izhikevich neurons were modelled in this experiment.

```
machineName      = 192.168.240.253
version          = 3
#down_cores     = None
#down_chips     = None
#bmp_names      = None
#auto_detect_bmp = False
#turn_off_machine = False
machineTimeStep = 2000
timeScaleFactor = 5
#enable_reinjection = True
```

Figure 117: Modifying the '.spynaker.cfg' file to calibrate the board to support the simulation of more Izhikevich neurons.

```
2017-05-20 14:14:23 ERROR: 0, 0, 5: WATCHDOG IZK_curr_exp_st
2017-05-20 14:14:24 WARNING: The reinjector on 0, 0 has dropped 1978 packets.
2017-05-20 14:14:24 WARNING: The reinjector on 0, 0 has detected that 49723 packets were dumped
from a core failing to take the packet. This often occurs when the executable has crashed or has not
been given a multicast packet callback. It can also result from the core taking too long to process each
packet. These packets were reinjected and so this number is likely a overestimate.
Traceback (most recent call last):
...spinnman.exceptions.SpinnmanException: 1 cores have reached an error state CPUState.WATCHDOG:
```

Figure 118: System crashes occur if more than 100 neurons are simulated at once.

This experiment represents a novel contribution consisting of a test case for the SpiNNaker system that showcases the capability of SpiNNaker in simulating a synaptic model of an Izhikevich neuron. The system successfully uses this model to produce a rhythmic pattern of network activity similar to Izhikevich experiments (Izhikevich, 2006, pg 253). What was learnt was that plasticity is regulated homeostatically by STDP.

This informs the development of the next version of sPyNNaker and the SpiNNaker hardware and exposes some limitations since the system cannot support longer simulations without specialist knowledge on how to correctly calibrate the configuration of network simulations using 'spynaker.cfg' or possibly more powerful hardware. This restricted the capacity to observe the effects of longer term plasticity for this experiment.

This experiment could be improved upon by finding the right calibration for the SpiNNaker board in order to support the simulation of more neurons to observe the effects of plasticity on larger scale networks. This will produce results with activity more akin to neural networks found in the human brain.

8.0 Conclusion

This section will conclude the report by reflecting on the project achievements, future directions to advance this work and learning outcomes from the project as a whole.

8.1 Review of project outcomes

At the beginning of the project, a set of objectives were set to achieve the stated aim of this project, "...to understand and report on capabilities and limitations of SpiNNaker and to extend the neuromorphic platform to facilitate more complex neural simulations." The extent of how the objectives have been met are reviewed.

Objectives:

- Research the hardware architecture of the SpiNNaker platform

This has been successfully achieved by providing a focused overview of the design philosophy, hardware implementation and how the programming approach is informed by the event driven model. However due to space constraints a selection of the key features of the SpiNNaker system were chosen to be reported on. This will be enormously beneficial to those desiring to familiarise themselves with the SpiNNaker technology by providing an introduction of the most important aspects of the system. More could be reported about quantitative drivers, bisection bandwidth, memory spaces, router internals and fault tolerance but were considered additional details with no direct relevance to the project. Explanation of such details can be found in (Furber et al., 2013).

- Research the design architecture of sPyNNaker API to gain a thorough understanding of important functions for neural modelling.

This has also been successfully achieved by illuminating important design aspects of the sPyNNaker API with regards to code separation and API files involved in process critical for neural modelling.

Again, only a subset of API aspects was documented but will contribute to those who want to use the sPyNNaker API to create networks of neurons.

- Extend the sPyNNaker architecture by implementing a compartmental neuron model based on a biological pyramidal neuron

This was successfully achieved by adding additional C code to extend the C functionality of the sPyNNaker API. An extensive knowledge of the sPyNNaker API was required as well as the hardware architecture regarding the use of SDRAM and node-local memory in storing and retrieving data.

- Identify an algorithmic implementation approach of the Urbanczik-Senn plasticity rule suitable for SpiNNaker that utilises the implemented neuron model

This was successfully achieved by proposing an algorithmic that is feasible for implementation given the hardware and software constraints. A deep understanding of the STDP process implemented on sPyNNaker was required as well as an understanding of the unintuitive mathematics underpinning the Urbanczik-Senn plasticity rule.

- Bring the implementation approach of the plasticity rule to a suitable stage to take forward into future work and document it

The success of this objective could be considered a matter of perspective. On one hand the problems encountered have been documented and could serve to inform others who adopt the same kind of approach of the potential issues. This could help save time and other approaches could be utilised. However on the other hand, due to time constraints a testable implementation was not achieved and the performance of the rule was not able to be observed to verify the correctness of the proposed solution. In the context of the objective this could be deemed a partial success as the problems and challenging aspects of design were extensively discussed to inform others on the crucial problems to be overcome should they wish to carry on implementation.

8.2 Achievements

Below is a summary of personal and project achievements:

- Successfully extended the sPyNNaker API by introducing a new method of distinguishing inputs and increasing the state space of the neuron. This was achieved by enhancing the neuron model to receive two excitatory inputs instead of one.
- Documented the limitations and capabilities of SpiNNaker in adopting the proposed implementation approach for the Urbanczik-Senn plasticity rule.
- Contributed to the advancement of neuromorphic computing system capabilities and the field of computational neuroscience
- Provided suitable documentation on the novelty of the technology from a hardware and software standpoint.

8.3 Future work

This section will discuss work that could further what was done in this project.

8.3.1 Neuron model

The adoption of ring and input buffers along with the inputs type as an input 'channel' was a design assumption to abstract the functionality of dendritic compartments. This is due to a lack of suitable infrastructure to support explicit dendritic compartments in SpiNNaker due to optimisation for just point neuron models. Future work could involve adding dendritic compartment processors as additional memory buffers proposed by Knight and Furber (2016) to perform identical functions to the neuron processors to receive synaptic input from synapse processors.

The compartment processors will have their own voltages and receive membrane voltages from other neuron and dendritic compartments. They will be updated according to a time driven algorithm just like the somatic compartment of current neuron models. It is imagined that this would involve a substantial reworking of the underlying architecture by allocating additional memory buffers either in software or more robustly in hardware. This would enable a membrane potential variable to be used in the dendritic compartment to avoid having to use the input buffer currents which are cumbersome to access in the current architecture. It could also be more readily accessed if it resided in the same memory locations access by synaptic processors in STDP and allows it to be retrieved for the right neuron through a simple interface function similar to the `neuron_model_get_membrane_voltage()` in the neuron model component.

A further design modification is to pass in an array of inputs to the neuron model from the synapse type. This would allow identification of the inputs from each different sources instead receiving the total excitatory input at each time step. Currently the input buffer contains one value, which is decayed and passed to the neuron. An input struct could be defined in "neuron_typedefs" or "synapse_type.h" to give an ID to each input and an interface function could be defined in `synapse_type.h` to retrieve the inputs (Rowley, 2017).

8.3.2 Learning rule

While introducing a modulating voltage was relatively straightforward, retrieving this value from the correct neuron ID was the outstanding issue. More work in implementing the proposed solution could be done to verify the results. This will allow testing of the proposed design to evaluate its effectiveness.

8.4 Final reflections

This project has enabled me to undertake dynamic and exciting research in an advanced field at the forefront of scientific research. However I learnt that being involved in cutting edge scientific research involving experimental technology in its infancy comes with potential as well as many risks. Only through conducting extensive research into SpiNNaker and the sPyNNaker API could I understand what really was required, and it was more than what could be done in a Final Year Project.

The extent of the novelty of the technology was of particular surprise, especially the implemented models in sPyNNaker which trailed far behind PyNN. This made it difficult to conduct suitable experiments as only simple models were implemented. The constraints around the hardware provided the biggest challenge as there was a lack of global memory which meant that neuron and synapse variables were stored in different places and could only be accessed at certain points in

execution flow through DMA operations. It is recommended that anyone who decides to advance the work conducted be aware of the limitations of the board, that it is still in an experimental state. Nonetheless, many personal learning outcomes applicable to life beyond university have been achieved which I will take forward with me as I advance in life.

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VIII. Appendices

Appendix A

This section provides instructions to install the SpiNNaker Development Tools.

Requirements:

1. A SpiNNaker system board
2. Ethernet cable to connect system board with host machine
3. Python 2.7
4. Linux based operating system – not strictly required but is highly recommended
5. The submitted archive

Up to date instructions for installing the development tools can be found at <https://spinnakermanchester.github.io/development/devenv.html>

Additional API modules such as sPyNNaker7 (<https://github.com/SpiNNakerManchester/sPyNNaker7>) may need installing to be compatible with STDP_network.py found in the archive.

After setting up the build tools, to run the program, example2.py or STDP_network.py can be run in a code editor such as Eclipse with the board connected via ethernet

Note: Due to the infancy of the technology, the API modules may undergo enhancements and modifications by the SpiNNaker development team. It is plausible that fundamental changes to the structure of the API have been made that render the submitted source code incompatible with current build tools.

